

B-WaterSmart, FIWARE based interoperability framework

Deliverable 3.1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869171. The publication reflects only the authors' views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

B-WaterSmart, FIWARE based interoperability framework

D3.1: B-WaterSmart, FIWARE based interoperability framework

Summary

This document is focused on providing a set of guidelines based on state of the art technologies and creating a framework to allow water-related software tools to increase their interoperability features. It includes a detailed analysis of the set of 22 software tools involved in the 5 Living labs of the B-WaterSmart project, studying potential interoperability improvements and exploring potential interaction among them. In addition, the concept of Interoperability Maturity levels is introduced, which provides a classification/ranking approach for any tool considering their interoperability features. At the same time, a reference architecture based on FIWARE components is proposed for new development or refactoring processes. Then, to enable the evolution of any tool, the document defines guidelines in a roadmap shape oriented on two main decisions for an interoperable software: the architecture, and the data models to use. Finally, some results in the project implementation phase and some potential interoperability results on Living Labs are shown.

Deliverable number

D3.1

Work package

WP3

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Planned delivery date

30/04/2022

Actual delivery date

29/04/2022 (V1.0; revised V1.3 in summer 2022)

Dissemination level

- PU = Public
- PP = Restricted to other programme participants
- RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium.
Please specify: _____
- CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium

History of changes

Version	Date	Description
1.0	29-04-2022	Submission (in time)
After submission changes		
1.1	03-05-2022	Fix links and changes in data models analysis document
1.2	20-05-2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Tool fact sheets document and data models analysis regarding tool #34• LEN minor changes
1.3	08-06-2022	Correct affiliation problems (NTUA).
Upon request of the consortium, V1.0 was rejected by the EC in order to enable submission of the voluntarily revised version V1.3.		

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AGROVOC	Agriculture Vocabulary
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BACNET	Building Automation Control network
BASEFORM	Aggregate Formula LDA
BWS	B-WaterSmart
CB	Context Broker
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
CET	CETAQUA
CoaP	Constrained Application Protocol
CoP	Community of Practice
CSV	Comma-Separated Values file
DAP	Data Application Product
DSBA	Data Spaces Businedd Alliance
EBSI	European Blockchain Services Infrastructure
EC	European Comission
eIDAS	electronic Identification, Authentication and trust Services
ENG	Engineering
EPA	Environment Protection Agency
ETSI ISG CIM	European Telecommunications Standards Institute Industry Specification Group Context Information Management
EYDAP	Athens Water Supply and Sewerage Company
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GA	Grant Agreement
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
ICCS	Institute Of Communication and Computer Systems
IML	Interoperability Maturity Level
InAll	Innovation Alliance
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Standards Organization
IT	Information Technolofy
JDBC	Java DataBase Connectivity

JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KWR	KWR Water B.V.
LEN	Lisboa E-Nova
LL	Living Lab
MQTT	MQ Telemetry Transport
NGSI	Next Generation Service Interfaces
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OPC-UA	Open Platform of Communications Unified Architecture
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PAP	Policy Administration Point
PDF	Portable Document Format
PDP	Policy Decision Point
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
PNG	Portable Graphics Format
QGIS	Quantum Geographic Information System
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
ROI	Return Of Investment
SAREF	Smart Applications REFerence
SINTEF	Stiftelsen for industriell og teknisk forskning
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SSO	Single Sign-On
TER	Total Expense Ratio
TM	Tele Management
TP	Technology Product
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WEFE	Water, Energy, Food, Environment
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant
XACML	Extensible Access Control Markup Language
XLS	Microsoft Excel spreadsheet file
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Executive summary

Water is one of the world's most trending topics and multifaceted issues nowadays. A set of innovative solutions (e.g., use of alternative water resources, industrial and urban water reuse, improved balance of water-energy-nutrients and increased efficiency in the water sector, selection, co-development and application of interlinked cost-effective technologies, concepts and water-smart data solutions) will come about as a result of effective collaboration, communication and knowledge exchange in the scope of B-WaterSmart project. Research has shown that when people from different backgrounds and interests work together, they have a better chance of coming up with new ideas that can be effectively applied at the local level, as well as scaled up and disseminated.

On the other hand, FIWARE has been implemented and released in the last years thanks to the support of the EC as an Open Source set of tools to enable the smart digital future of Europe. The usage of FIWARE is very tied to the interoperability concept as it is driving key standards for breaking information silos and enabling data sharing policies and data economies at cross-sectorial level. Indeed, the water domain initiatives have been the most relevant in the FIWARE community with several new data models defined to share data among water parties¹.

Considering this rich environment, this document aims to guide firstly the B-WaterSmart development teams, being useful to any other water domain team, on the adoption of interoperability principles by reviewing the state of the art on interoperability approaches, focusing on the capabilities of FIWARE technologies and community. Taking advantage of the fact that the project involves several development teams with heterogeneous backgrounds, portfolios, and objectives for tools dedicated to the water domain; a mentoring and assessment process was carried out to engage them in this new interoperability approach according to their needs, capabilities, and maturity levels. To this end, the project team has analysed the set of 22 software tools involved in the 5 Living Labs to define a set of use cases and requirements aiming to study potential interoperability improvements on each tool and exploring potential interaction among them.

In fact, the concept of Interoperability Maturity levels has been founded during this process to provide, based on FIWARE technologies, an approach for the assessment of tools' maturity levels considering their implemented/needed interoperability features and also to provide a roadmap and framework to identify the possible evolution stages.

Regarding the structure, this document starts by introducing the objectives of the B-WaterSmart task designed to this end, and the main concepts regarding interoperability and FIWARE. In a second step, the document presents the guidelines to follow when developing or refactoring a tool aiming to be interoperable, highlighting the main topics to address. Also, the document focuses on defining a set of interoperability maturity levels, using examples, to provide a clearer interoperability roadmap. Then, the results of analysing, together with each tool owner, the 22 software tools are presented in a set of: (i) tool factsheets, providing a generic description of each tool; (ii) use cases, giving a general idea of the main features/usages for each tool and the data managed, and (iii) requirements, pointing out the main interoperability requirements for each tool. This work allows us to define a baseline for each tool and also the potential needs.

¹ <https://github.com/smart-data-models/SmartWater>

Next sections present a reference architecture based on FIWARE components that allows reusing some parts depending on the specific needs of each tool. In addition, a study of the available data solutions in the market is presented, starting with standard formats and ontologies, going through the data solutions given by FIWARE, based on NGSI or NGSI-LD and the smart data models initiative, and finalizing with the proposal of data models per tool and the presentation of a new data model for water smartness.

Finally, the work done and main results during this process is presented as well as the potential interoperability results within the scope of the B-WaterSmart project are highlighted in three Living Labs.

Acknowledgments

The WP3 team responsible for the preparation of the D3.1 document would like to thank all Living Lab owners and partners for their contribution to the development and review of this document. Special acknowledgement goes to the Tool Owners and the teams involved in Task3.1 who are listed below:

Alicante Living Lab

- ***RE-ACTOR***: Miquel Sarrias, Mario Ruiz (CET)

Bodø Living Lab

- ***Nessie System***: Panagiotis Kossieris (ICCS)
- ***Azure Cosmos DB and Environmental Dashboard***: Vemund Kristiansen, Ola Johan Holand, David Steffenbauer (NORDKONTAKT)

Flanders Living Lab

- ***Stormwater Reuse Management System***: Stefan Kroll (AQUA), Joris Ingeborg (VITO)
- ***Urban Water Optioneering Tool***: Stavroula Manouri (ICCS), Dimitrios Bouziotas (KWR)
- ***QMRA+***: Alifita Ariestwi, Patrick Smeets (KWR)
- ***SuTRa***: Geertje Pronk (KWR)

East Frisia Living Lab

- ***Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS Tool***: Christine Kübeck, Kristina Wencki (IWW)
- ***Urban Water Optioneering Tool***: Stavroula Manouri (ICCS), Dimitrios Bouziotas (KWR)
- ***Short-Term Demand Forecasting Tool***: Marcel Juschak (IWW)

Lisbon Living Lab

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- ***Urban Water Cycle Observatory Tool***: Rui Mendes, Maria Rodrigues (LEN)
- ***Climate-readiness Certification Tool / Energy efficiency certificates / AQUA+***: Pedro Cardoso, Ana Poças (ADENE)

Venice Living Lab

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Transversal tool

- ***Water-smartness assessment framework***: Rita Ugarelli, Audun Vennesland (SINTEF)

Introduction

1.1 Objectives

This document has been developed to fulfill the objectives of the Task 3.1 of the B-WaterSmart(BWS) project as per DoA and is structured to understand the context of the task.

Task 3.1 is aimed mainly at developing a FIWARE-based interoperability approach for water-smart applications and data. To achieve it, the proposed approach is to work on the following three main points:

- Definition of **use cases and requirements** for new tools developed in T3.2-T3.7, as well as initial use cases for the dashboard to be developed in T3.9 and use cases for the water-smartness framework (WP6)
- Definition of **a reference architecture** collaborating with the Fiware4Water project to support tool design based on the following three ideas:
 - FIWARE I/O data standardization
 - Assessment of Linked Data Usage (JSON-LD)
 - Investigate how to integrate proprietary (legacy) water monitoring and actuation systems in the demo cases with the reference architecture
- To provide **a framework** enabling the interoperability of any tool by clarifying the process for developing agents, gateways/adaptors for integration with the proposed architecture

1.2 Structure

This deliverable is structured in the following way. First and foremost, it is important to understand the concepts upon which Task 3.1 is based, as well as the scope of this work. The needed concepts, definitions and an overview of the framework used to achieve the Task 3.1 objectives are all included in the Introduction, as a technical baseline, which also includes a brief description of the project tools involved.

Once the concepts and the context are clear, in Introduction B-WaterSmart Interoperability guidelines is provided the core of this deliverable, the guidelines and the steps tool owners must follow if they want to be part of the ecosystem of interoperable tools. This will allow the tools to exchange useful information.

A Tools analysis exposes the starting point of this project. This includes the list of tool factsheets with relevant information and the current features of each tool, such as, data types, technologies, architecture, objectives of the tool, data models, etc., i.e. in a nutshell, all of the necessary information for accurate planning and analysis. In addition, a first use case analysis of each tool is provided, and the initial requirements are specified after analysing the previous data.

B-WaterSmart FIWARE-base Reference Architecture describes the reference architecture to be used with the BWS tools and is based on FIWARE technologies by using as inspiration the architecture of FIWARE4WATER project (López, 2020).

B-WaterSmart Proposed Data solutions provides different alternatives to manage the data to be exchanged by the tools using interoperable formats and semantic relations. Solutions are given using ontologies or the smart data models provided by the FIWARE community.

Finally, in the B-WaterSmart implementation results last chapter, it is described how the above have been applied to the living lab tools as well as their way from the development phase to being part of an interoperable community (B-WaterSmart).

1.3 Main concepts and definitions

As a baseline to introduce the guidelines to develop a FIWARE architecture solution, it is important to clarify the concepts that are used in any FIWARE solution in order to have a clear understanding of the components needed and used:

- **Data model (domain data model):** It is the definition of the concepts and their attributes shaping the data that will be managed in a use case. It determines the structure of the data (how data is related) and its type (string characters, number, dates, etc...).

Smart Data model²: A smart data model includes three elements: **The schema**, or technical representation of the model defining the technical data types and structure, **the specification**, a human readable document, and **the examples** of the payloads for **NGSiv2 and NGSI-LD** versions. All data models are **public and of royalty-free nature**. The licensing mode grants 3 rights to the users: Free use, Free modification, Free sharing of the modifications. Moreover, it is importance to notice that the water related data models are the result coming from different H2020 projects (FIWARE4WATER, NAIADES, SCOREWATER and AQUA3S) under the initiative of DIGITALWATER2020³

- **(Reference) Architecture:** In terms of software engineering, a software architecture refers to the structure of a software system. It means the software components that compose the structure, relations between components and the properties of each one. A reference architecture is an architecture that provides recommended structures and integrations of IT products and services to form a solution. The reference architecture includes accepted industry best practices or recommended technological components.
- **Interoperability:** The ability of two or more systems or components to exchange information and to use the information that has been exchanged (IEEEExplore, 1991). In general terms, there is a list of interoperability layers defined, which includes⁴: **Interoperability governance, Integrated public service governance, Legal interoperability, Organisational interoperability, Technical/syntactic interoperability, and Semantic interoperability**. Regarding the scope of the project, it is important to make special focus on **semantic** and **syntactic** interoperability definitions (Rocha, Espirito-Santo, & Abrishambaf, 2020):

² <https://www.fiware.org/developers/smart-data-models/>

³ <https://www.fiware4water.eu/news/synergy-group-digitalwater2020>

⁴ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/nifo-national-interoperability-framework-observatory/3-interoperability-layers>

- **Technical / syntactic interoperability:** Two or more systems capable of communicating and exchanging data over specified data formats and communication protocols. It is necessary to provide an interface for each schema, such as REST APIs. The message content needs to be serialized to be sent in a format, e.g., XML or JSON. The sender encodes the message, and the receiver decodes the message. Incompatibility occurs when the receiver decoding rules are incompatible with the sender encoding rules.
- **Semantic interoperability:** Is the ability to automatically interpret the information exchanged meaningfully and accurately in order to produce useful results as defined by end users of both systems. To achieve semantic interoperability, both sides must defer to a common information exchange reference model. The content of the information exchange requests are unambiguously defined.

In the scope of B-WaterSmart project, the main technical solution proposed to achieve interoperability among digital tools is by using FIWARE technologies, which are supported by the EC (European Commission) with collaboration with standardization bodies like ETSI and facilitate interoperability in real time environments thanks to the usage of context brokers. Indeed, the usage of the standardized semantic data models for sharing data among parties and software components allows to keep the contextual information around each value in the process. So, keeping the contextual information on data allows ad-hoc data aggregations and/or global integrations from heterogeneous systems that later on can run autonomous processing models to get the most of the available data and creating powerful solutions able to deal with broader and more complex decision making processes.

- **Interoperability through NGSIv2:** NGSI means “New Generation Service Interface” and is a protocol to manage context information. It provides operations like the following:
 - Manage the Context Information about Context Entities, for example the lifetime and quality of information.
 - Access (query, subscribe/notify) to the available Context Information about Context Entities.

The FIWARE version of the Open Mobile Alliance (OMA) NGSI interface is a RESTful API via HTTP. Its purpose is to exchange context information. The two main interaction types are:

- One-time queries for context information
 - Subscriptions for context information updates (and the corresponding notifications)
- **Semantic interoperability through NGSI-LD⁵:** NGSI-LD is an evolution of the NGSI v2 information model, which has been modified to improve support for linked data (entity relationships), property graphs and semantics (exploiting the capabilities offered by JSON-LD). This work has been conducted under the ETSI ISG CIM⁶ initiative and the updated specification has been branded as NGSI-LD \mathcal{L} . The main constructs of NGSI-LD are *Entity*, *Property* and *Relationship*. NGSI-LD Entities (instances) can be the subject of Properties or Relationships. In terms of the traditional NGSI v2 data model, Properties can be

⁵ <https://documenter.getpostman.com/view/513743/SVYjSMgh>

⁶ [https://docbox.etsi.org/isg/cim/open/CIM\(20\)000090_Introduction_NGSI-LD.pdf](https://docbox.etsi.org/isg/cim/open/CIM(20)000090_Introduction_NGSI-LD.pdf)

⁷ https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/CIM/001_099/009/01.01.01_60/gs_CIM009v010101p.pdf

seen as the combination of an attribute and its value. Relationships allow establishing associations between instances using linked data.

- **Publish/Subscribe pattern**⁸: Publish/Subscribe is an interaction pattern that characterizes the exchange of messages between publishing and subscribing clients through a component named “message broker”. Subscribers express interest in receiving messages and publishers simply publish messages without specifying the recipients for a message. The publish/subscribe message exchange is decoupled and anonymous. That is, publishers don't know subscribers' identities and if there are any subscribers with matching interests at all. This supports a many-to-many style of communication, where data sources publish to a message broker and data sinks subscribe.
- **Message Broker (component)**: As we can see in Figure 1, a message broker is an intermediary computer program module that translates a message from the formal messaging protocol of the sender to the formal messaging protocol of the receiver. Message brokers are elements in telecommunication or computer networks where software applications communicate by exchanging formally defined messages. In the context of publish/subscribe pattern “message broker” publishers post messages in “message broker”, and subscribers register subscriptions with that broker, letting the broker perform the filtering. The broker routes messages from publishers to subscribers. In addition, the broker may prioritize messages in a queue before routing them.

Figure 1 Schema of communication between Publishers and Subscribers through subscriptions to message broker information ⁹

⁸ https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007%2F978-0-387-39940-9_1181

⁹ <https://medium.com/@danieltoo/primeros-pasos-con-fiware-fe88b53b8895>

1.4 B-WaterSmart Interoperability overview

The objective of the task is mainly to develop a FIWARE-based interoperability approach for water-smart applications and data exchange. However, one must keep in mind that B-WaterSmart partners have no contractual obligation to implement FIWARE solutions, however their contributions will be needed to study the water sector needs and status. In parallel, the interoperability/FIWARE experts in the project, namely ENG, SINTEF, ICCS and EUT, are implementing an engaging task for tool owners by explaining the benefits of interoperability and the impact of it. So, the B-WaterSmart project is encouraged to increase awareness on using FIWARE related technologies to be aligned with the adopted reference architecture in the water sector.

1.4.1 Why to be interoperable?

Basically, interoperability allows for the joint and orderly management of information. For a better decision on addressing this topic, this section highlights the main advantages and disadvantages of it:

- **Advantages:**
 - **Avoids duplication:** It allows us to have one source of trustworthy information while avoiding modifiable copies of the information.
 - **Guaranteed data cohesion:** information is managed efficiently and controlled by all parties by agreement/convention guaranteeing its consistency.
 - **Accessibility:** It is possible to work and operate in a consistent manner with various tools that work with data from the same domain, ensuring that the information is available and accessible to all parties, systems, and people.
 - **Capacity to discover and be discovered:** The usage of interoperable formats allows one to find interesting data sources when automatic processes are searching on the internet. Example: Spiders are software applications used to discover web resources and make them visible on search engines depending on the contents of a common and standard file called robots.txt
 - **Easy integration:** Interoperable systems are easily integrated with others when using standardized formats where everybody knows which data is shared and which format it is used. At industrial stage OPC-UA¹⁰, BACNET¹¹, MODBUS¹² and other standards allow the communication and automatization of machines and control units.
 - **Improves productivity:** The capacity to integrate new systems in an interoperable solution allows us to improve productivity and to avoid the development of ad-hoc and costly systems. Example: In a manufacturing line, it is easier to use robots from various vendors that communicate based on a single communication protocol.
 - **Reusable resources and knowledge:** Interoperable solutions following standard communication and formats are easily integrated rather than creating/adopting ad-hoc data models per each application where misunderstandings among concepts and values are frequent.

¹⁰ <https://opcfoundation.org/about/opc-technologies/opc-ua/>

¹¹ <http://www.bacnet.org/>

¹² <https://modbus.org/>

- **Keep confidence/reliability** on data: Data shared in interoperable environments can be managed by reliable agents and prevented from being modified by others. AGROVOC¹³ is a well-known thesaurus for the agricultural domain maintained by FAO to organize their common concepts.

Worthy ROI: Interoperability may require more time than usual to be applied and the investment return is difficult to determine. However, with a good strategy, it will allow for an easier expansion of the product capabilities and the identification of commercial opportunities.

- **Disadvantages:**

- **Cost of integration:** Depending on the number of systems and their complexity (data formats and communication needs), the effort needed to be interoperable could be seen as initially too costly.
- **Lack of standards:** In some non-industrial sectors, data sharing is not a common practice, probably due to a lack of interest in investing in the definition of interoperability standards. This lack of standards makes it difficult to achieve data exchange in these sectors. Fortunately, in recent years European Commission (, the EC) and some companies have been investing in novel standards for data interoperability in the WEFE (Water, Energy, Food, environment) sectors in order to address this situation¹⁴ .
- **Over-standardization of particular domains:** In some domains a huge list of standards has been defined, discouraging the use of interoperable solutions, fearing the selection of a non-broadly adopted standard.
- **Privacy issues:** Personal or private data, which is regulated by the EU and national legislation, could imply the need for anonymization and other costly processes.

Once enumerated the interoperability disadvantages and challenges to face off, we will introduce in section 0 how FIWARE and its components could help to address them in a suitable way.

1.4.2 Impact

Nowadays, droughts and water scarcity due to climatic change, massive agriculture, and improper management of water resources, are problems that are increasing and causing direct and indirect effects, such as water scarcity for humans and problems in economic sectors. The B-WaterSmart project tries to provide an approach to solve or address these challenges. Specifically, a way of tackling these issues is through interoperability of key tools from different water domains, which can offer a specific point of view of different contexts, with opportunities for mutual learning and having an impact in different sectors:

- **Social:** Thanks to data exchange among water utilities, improved water management strategies using different data sources can be discovered, applied and validated in Living Labs, urban areas or municipalities. These practices can derive benefits for society, i.e., improved daily

¹³ <https://agrovoc.fao.org/browse/agrovoc/en/>

¹⁴ https://www.sim4nexus.eu/userfiles/Deliverable_D4.4.pdf

habits (e.g. water saving) of their inhabitants and increased awareness about correct water management. Indeed, once validated, and due to the nature of the interoperable solutions, they can be quickly replicated to other locations, benefitting their population and the environment.

- **Economy:** Creation of novel business models based on interoperability/circular economy and water-smartness and improvement of resource (water, infrastructure, facilities) management, resulting in costs savings or worthwhile investments, enabling replicability and upscaling of BWS tools, fostering systemic innovation and increasing transferability of the solutions.
- **Environmental:** The exchange of data among all actors in the water distribution chain of a river basin can lead to better water policies, better optimization of water consumption by all types of consumers, an increased availability to other/newer players and sustainable usage, leading to the preservation of all ecosystems along the basin.

1.4.3 Tools per Living Lab involved

This section provides the collection of tools that have been co-designed in the Living Labs of the B-WaterSmart project, as well as for the Water-smartness assessment framework and the Water-smartness assessment tool (#34) which are multi-site. For all Living Labs, the purpose of each tool is described. This kind of information is useful to create an overview of the tools and technical capabilities involved in the project. The number of each tool corresponds to the identifier assigned in the GA and in this document, it is kept to preserve the coherence within the project.

ALICANTE LL	
TOOL	DESCRIPTION
(#18) RE-ACTOR	Real time water quality and risk monitoring to ensure acceptability of the different water end-users and visualization of the economic and environmental benefits of using the water. Engagement of stakeholders in decision-making through simulation of potential water reuse scenarios in the municipality

LISBON LL	
TOOL	DESCRIPTION
(#17) Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action	City and sector prioritization and decision-making environment, based on sets of key analytics, including water, energy and nutrient balances; performance, risk and cost analytics. Expressed numerically and graphically on a georeferenced 2D/3D cityscape environment. Fully automatable with online data sources
(#20) Urban Water Cycle	Visualization instrument for monitoring and communicating performance in water dimension, support urban planning and

Observatory	decision making, by providing a set of data analytics, publicly about the city and privately for single entities
(#24) Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model	Hydraulic and water quality modelling of reclaimed water distribution network, capable of exporting to EPANET ¹⁵ input file format and incorporating sensor data (e.g., chlorine residuals, temperature, turbidity, pH). Compatible with other Baseform modules in the project.
(#25) Water-energy-P balance planning	Module for planning support, extending network water and energy balance analytics to include P balance, mapping supply-demand and alternative sources
(#27) Risk Assessment for Urban Water Reuse module	A risk assessment tool based on European regulation (Regulation (EU) 2020/741 ¹⁶) and ISO standards (TC 282 Water Reuse ¹⁷) to facilitate health and environmental (surface and ground water) risk assessment and management for safe water reuse. It allows for quantitative and/or qualitative expression of likelihood and consequence, outputting results on the georeferenced 2D/3D environment and on the planning-support capabilities
(#33) Climate-readiness Certification Tool	Toolkit for ‘ Water Smart for Climate-Ready ’ Building Certificates
(#33.1) Energy efficiency certificates	This tool creates energy certificates based in the answers from formulars, supervised by experts of the energy domain. The current study is for three scenarios: households, buildings, neighborhood
(#33.2) AQUA+	AQUA+ provides an overall performance of the household, reporting what you can do better and how is your performance in terms of efficiency and consumption.

EAST FRISIA LL

TOOL	DESCRIPTION
(#22) Urban Water	UWOT will be used to simulate alternative water demand and

¹⁵ <https://www.epa.gov/water-research/epanet>

¹⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32020R0741>

¹⁷ <https://www.iso.org/committee/4856734.html>

Optioneering Tool	supply options under different climatic and demand change scenarios. The main objective has been the assessment of the available water quality and quantity under conditions of climate change via model-based forecast.
(#23) Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS tool	Identification of communal and industrial water requirements and matching these with regionally available water resources, calculating, where necessary, transport and treatment requirements.
(#28) Short-Term Demand Forecasting Tool	Automatization of day-to-day water demand forecasting. Performs highly decentralized water demand analysis and allocation of water resources, based on smart meter data.

VENICE LL	
TOOL	DESCRIPTION
(#16) Water reuse strategic platform	Freshwater saving and WasteWater Reuse (WWR). Ranks reuse opportunities for preserving freshwater, allowing mitigation of barriers at multiple levels (requirements and infrastructures needs, geographical, political and regulatory issues)
(#19) Sludge management platform	Sewage sludge valorization. Ranks the best treatment and disposal solutions, in relation to the socio-economical and geographical context and taking into account low carbon footprint and energy recovery logics
(#32) Digital Enabler	Supports the development of #16 and #19

FLANDERS LL	
TOOL	DESCRIPTION
(#21) Stormwater Reuse Management System	A system that allows the combination of operational management of a stormwater basin and a connected subirrigation system for groundwater recharge and direct irrigation; optimizes system functioning, based on real time data and model predictions
(#22) Urban Water Optioneering Tool	UWOT will be used to model a case of regional water management where multiple technologies can be combined to design a robust, water-smart system. This is done in this case in two ways: a) Use of alternative water sources, with the reuse of WWTP effluent to cover different water needs. Scenarios of WWTP

	<p>effluent reuse will be drawn with the help of regional stakeholders.</p> <p>b) Improved stormwater management, with the installation of smart retention ponds in urban and agricultural areas, which flood-proof downstream regions, increase infiltration and reduce pressure on groundwater. Flanders also includes a pilot of a smart retention pond, so that findings from this pilot will be used and upscaled for the model.</p>
(#26) QMRA+	Simulation tool that combines data chosen from the user with generic information and provides a report or a table with the level of risk as a result.
(#31) SuTRa (former ASR-pro tool)	Predicts pathogen transport properties as well as concentration of pathogens after subsurface storage.

BODØ

TOOL	DESCRIPTION
(#29) Nessie System	Nessie's implementation in Bodo case targets the householders. Specifically, a web application, based on Nessie technology, will be developed to enable householders to monitor the water consumption of their households, using data from smart water meters. The application will integrate seamlessly with third-party algorithms for the detection of leakages and bursts.
(#30) Azure Cosmos DB and Environmental Dashboard	This tool will be able to display the current state of water network on home buildings, monitoring parameters some water parameters and detecting leakages

TRANSVERSAL (multi-site)

TOOL	DESCRIPTION
(#34) Water smartness assessment framework (WP6) and tool (T3.9)	<p>The framework consists of structured libraries of strategic objectives, assessment criteria and metrics to be selected while applying the methodology, which includes the following steps: setting the objectives, diagnosis, strategic plan development and monitoring loop.</p> <p>Main functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide a minimum set of metrics that allow for comparing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ the current state in relations to the Living Labs own objectives ○ developments over time and between cases. • Enhance adaptive management through yearly data-update of the framework to enhance flexibility,

	<p>experimentation, and learning.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance anticipatory capacity. <p>The Water-smartness framework will be implemented as an online dashboard, a tool to assess the overall gain in water-smartness and sustainability for the LLs.</p>
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1.5 FIWARE framework

1.5.1 FIWARE description

FIWARE is an open-source initiative defining a universal set of standards for the development and global deployment of Smart Solutions for Internet applications. FIWARE tries to provide a totally open, public, and free architecture as well as a set of specifications that allows developers, service providers, companies, and other organizations to gather and manage context information, processing that information and informing external actors, enabling them to actuate and therefore alter or enrich the current context.¹⁸¹⁹²⁰

1.5.2 Components

The FIWARE platform is made up of open-source platform components that can be assembled with other third-party platform components to accelerate the development of smart solutions. These platform components provide APIs (application programming interfaces) whose specifications are public and royalty-free. In addition, they have an open-source reference implementation publicly available so that FIWARE providers can go to market quickly, with low-cost proposals.

The main and only mandatory component of any "Powered by FIWARE" platform or solution is the Context Broker (its reference implementation is called Orion Context Broker), which provides a fundamental function in any intelligent solution: the need to manage context information, allowing updates and access to context. The Context Broker²¹ is surrounded by a suite of additional platform components (Figure 2), which allow the provision of context data from various sources (Internet of Things, robots, and third-party systems) and provide support for data processing, analysis, and visualization, as well as for data access control, publication or monetization. In addition, it offers a series of tools that facilitate the implementation and configuration of FIWARE or third-party components and their integration with the Context Broker.

¹⁸ https://www.fiware.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/FIWARE_Foundation_Press_Kit_English.pdf

¹⁹ <https://www.fiware.org/developers/catalogue/>

²⁰ <https://www.fiware.org/news/etsi-releases-preliminary-specification-of-context-information-management-standard-api-leveraged-on-the-fiware-ngsi-api/>

²¹ <https://fiware-orion.readthedocs.io/en/master/>

Figure 2.- FIWARE sections of components ²²

The components of the FIWARE platform, also known as Generic Enablers, are described in this section in the following points: Context management, IoT, Robots and third-party systems, Processing, analysis and visualization of context data and Access management, publication and monetization of APIs and data from context.

1.5.2.1 Core context management

- **Orion Context Broker** ²³ is the central and mandatory component of any "Powered by FIWARE" platform or solution. It allows for managing context information in a highly decentralized and large-scale way. It provides the FIWARE NGSIv2 API, which is a simple and very powerful Restful API that allows updates, queries, or subscriptions to changes in context information. The Orion Context Broker maintains the current context information. However, context information evolves over time, creating a history of context. The following components are required to facilitate context history storage:
 - **Draco** ²⁴ is a connector between Orion Context Broker and a wide range of external systems such as MySQL, MongoDB, PostgreSQL, to process and persist context data. Also, can be used to filter and repost context data back into Orion.
 - **STH Comet** provides the means to store a short-term history of context data (usually months) in MongoDB.
 - **Cygnus** provides the means to manage context history that is created as a data stream. It can be injected into multiple data sinks, including some popular databases like

²² <https://www.fiware.org/developers/catalogue/>

²³ <https://fiware-orion.readthedocs.io/en/master/>

²⁴ <https://fiware-academy.readthedocs.io/en/latest/core/draco/index.html>

PostgreSQL, MySQL, MongoDB, or AWS DynamoDB, as well as Big Data platforms like Hadoop, Storm, Spark or Flink.

- **Quantum Leap** enables the storage of FIWARE NGSIv2 API data to a time series database, known as ngsi-tldb. It has a **CrateDB** translator with which the following advantages are provided:
 - Easy scalability with containerized database clustering
 - Geo-query support
 - SQL-like query language
 - Supported integration with visualization tools like Grafana
 -

With the introduction of the NGSI-LD specification, which allows for contextual interlinking provided by a linked data representation, context brokers supporting that specification have been developed. Currently the following NGSI-LD compliant context brokers are offered as alternatives to the Orion Context Broker described above:

- **Orion-LD**²⁵ is a FIWARE context broker that supports both the NGISv2 and NGSI-LD (currently the 1.3.1 version of NGSI-LD) specifications.
- **Stellio**²⁶ is an NGSI-LD context broker developed by EGM. Stellio uses a Neo4J²⁷ graph database and allows for temporal queries towards a TimescaleDB database.
- **Scorpio**²⁸ is an NGSI-LD context broker developed by NEC Laboratories Europe and NEC Laboratories India.

1.5.2.2 IoT, Robots and Third-party systems

There are several components that facilitate the interface with the Internet of Things (IoT), robots, and third-party systems in order to collect valuable context information or trigger actions in response to context updates:

- **IDAS** offers a wide range of IoT Agents that facilitate the interface with devices that use the most widely used IoT protocols (LWM2M over CoaP, JSON or UltraLight over HTTP / MQTT or OPC-UA), and offers a framework for the development of one's own IoT gents.

1.5.2.3 Processing, analysis, and visualization

There are several components that facilitate the processing, analysis or visualization of context information in order to implement the expected "smart behavior" in any application:

- **WireCloud** provides a powerful web mashup platform that facilitates the development of dashboards that are highly customizable by end users.
- **Knowage** offers a powerful Business Intelligence platform that enables business analysis on traditional sources and big data systems.
- **Kurento** enables real-time processing of multimedia. It supports the transformation of video cameras into sensors, as well as the incorporation of advanced application functions

²⁵ <https://github.com/FIWARE/context.Orion-LD>

²⁶ <https://github.com/stellio-hub/stellio-context-broker>

²⁷ <https://neo4j.com/>

²⁸ <https://github.com/ScorpioBroker/ScorpioBroker>

(integrated audiovisual communications, augmented reality, flexible media recording and playback, etc.).

- **Cosmos** allows easier analysis of large clusters of context information by integrating with the most popular Big Data platforms.
-

1.5.2.4 Context data/API management, publication, and monetization

As to secured access components in the architecture of any “Powered by FIWARE” the FIWARE catalogue has the following components:

- **Keyrock Identity Management** supports secure and private OAuth2-based user and device authentication, user profile management, disposition of personal data to preserve privacy, single sign-on (SSO), and identity federation across multiple management domains.
- **Wilma** supports proxy functions within OAuth2-based authentication schemes. It also implements PEP functions within an XACML-based access control scheme.
- **AuthZForce PDP / PAP** supports PDP / PAP functions within an access control scheme based on the XACML standard.

The FIWARE platform also provides components for publishing and monetizing context data resources, available through the Orion Context Broker core component:

- **CKAN** generic enabler brings a number of add-ons enabling to extend current capabilities of the world-leading CKAN Open Data publication platform to allow publication of datasets matching right-time context data, the assignment of access terms and policies to those datasets and the assignment of pricing and pay-per-use schemas to datasets.
- **Biz Framework** generic enabler brings back-end support for context API / Data monetization based on open TM Forum Business APIs²⁹.

1.5.3 Integration approached driven by the FIWARE Context Broker

As seen in the previous sections, FIWARE provides mature, open, and standard-based components and resources for building bridges among IT systems and for boosting data and service interoperability.

Integration driven by the FIWARE Context Broker GE (the core component of FIWARE) and by NGSI may be implemented at different levels (see next figure).

²⁹ <https://www.tmforum.org/oda/about-open-apis/>

Figure 3.- Three different integration levels driven by the Context Broker

At a basic level (Figure 3 a)), **smart solutions** can be fed by context data that are produced by sensors, devices and third-party systems and that are mediated by the Context Broker. At this level, the Context Broker provides a digital representation of such devices and sensors, allowing smart solutions to interact with them in a homogeneous, centralized, and standard way. This level of integration is typically used for delivering individual smart solutions that are dedicated to a specific system such as smart metering systems, leakage detection solutions or water treatment systems.

At an intermediate integration level (Figure 3 b)), the Context Broker can play the role of a data broker among **different systems within organizations**, thus enabling a system of systems view. This level of integration can typically be used for delivering integration among smart solutions such as smart metering systems, wastewater treatment systems or raw water management systems.

At an inter-organizational level (Figure 3 c)), FIWARE is part of the DSBA (Data Spaces Business Alliance), which will make broader the impact and scope of the FIWARE technologies, driving the adoption of **Data Spaces** across Europe and beyond. The development of Data Spaces is fostered by the Commission and supported by different industrial initiatives in many vertical domains, including GAIA-X, FIWARE. Data Spaces are seen as the key to achieving sovereign, interoperable and trustworthy data sharing **between organizations and society**, a critical step for the data economy of the future.

As the practice of data sharing is gradually growing over time, organizations often face significant obstacles that prevent them from reaping the direct benefits. This is where Data Spaces come into play, bringing together data providers, users and intermediaries, playing a key role in helping companies to extract value from data in a competitive way also through the application of Artificial Intelligence in the industrial field, based on interoperability, portability, sovereignty and trustworthiness.

The water domain may greatly benefit from such standardization and interoperability stream, at least by adopting the general principle and architectural guidelines that underpin the most advanced works.

From a practical point of view, as shown in Figure 4, IDSA (International Data Spaces Association) is delivering several components for creating Data Spaces, with particular emphasis on trust and data sovereignty. On the other hand, the FIWARE ecosystem is providing standard APIs (NGSI-LD), standard data models (Smart Data Models Initiative) and marketplace functionalities. Moreover, the FIWARE Context Broker technology was adopted in 2018 as one of the Building Blocks of the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) program and has proven to integrate smoothly with other relevant CEF Building Blocks for the creation of Data Spaces (e.g., eIDAS, EBSI). As a result, the close partnership between FIWARE and IDSA is guaranteeing the aligned contribution of both ecosystems to the success of Data Spaces based on Gaia-X.

Figure 4.- FIWARE and IDSA Technology building blocks for Data Spaces

2 B-WaterSmart Interoperability guidelines

This chapter offers the guidelines any development team should consider when designing or refactoring a tool. In addition, the concept of Interoperability Maturity levels are presented, making special attention to the ones defined by the FIWARE community and also adapting them to a more generic approach for generic maturity levels, putting as examples the B-WaterSmart tools.

2.1 B-WaterSmart Implementation guidelines

With the objective of guiding all tool owners and developers to make their tools interoperable, this section shows a roadmap with some paths that may lead to a higher level of interoperability. Figure 5 presents the workflow that any developer should follow to develop/refactor any software tool in order to enable it to exchange data in an interoperable way with two main paths to follow, using FIWARE based technologies or using alternatives.

The development of software tools is divided in 5 steps: **Planification & Analysis**, **Design**, **Development**, **Test** and **Deployment**. It is important to know how each step/level of development is related with the next one. Therefore, their interaction will be explained, highlighting the two steps where FIWARE is relevant for interoperability, the design and the development:

1. **Planification & Analysis:** This is the first step and at which the tool is conceived. Basically, at this stage the objective of the software tool is defined, as well as which data is obtained and how it is presented. It includes the requirements of the software and additionally a set of use cases to clarify the actions and how the components are connected. This step feeds the next one which will define the data management and the software architecture.
2. **Design:** In this part of the methodology, we decided with the developers decide the potential they will use of FIWARE in the design like data needs and the architecture of the tool. This decision was based on the results coming from the previous step, the use cases, and requirements.

2.1. Following a FIWARE approach two main points must be evaluated:

2.1.1. Data needs: Identify data sources and evaluate possible synergies with third parties or external data sources. Determine the granularity of data (valves, sensors, households, districts, cities, etc.) and evaluate how to process data in the case of external sources. When exchanging data with external providers/consumers, the selection of data models (NGSI-LD/NGSIV2) will be required. If there is no smart data model fitting the data requirements, it is recommended to report it to the FIWARE community, which might support its development and use approaches based on NGSIV2.

2.1.2. Architecture: Based on the requirements, the selection of the appropriate components by the FIWARE catalogue will be done according to its features in terms of security, data storage, data visualization, data acquisition, processing, and data sharing.

2.2. For non-FIWARE oriented solutions, several state-of-the-art options following different architectures are available to solve data needs. Section 5.1 shows some possibilities on data standardization for the water domain.

Figure 5. Development steps as part of an interoperability approach schema

3. **Development:** Once selected, the needed components to manage the data of a tool must be individually configured and adapted to the specific tool's needs.
 - 3.1. **Following a FIWARE approach:** FIWARE components use the Docker³⁰ technology data exchange and to build networks. Docker allows to pull components initialize them and set up configurations.
 - 3.2. **For non-FIWARE oriented solutions:** Developers must decide between available state of the art technologies to exchange data and create the needed enablers to format/structure the data.
4. **Test:** At this stage, the software is being tested. Developers and product owners check if it meets the requirements as described in the first point and examine the behaviour of the software. At this stage, bugs are detected and fixed.
5. **Deployment:** Once developers know the software has a solid performance being successful in all tests, it is time to deploy it in a production environment.

2.2 FIWARE maturity levels

According to FIWARE platform, there are two concepts or definitions that classify the solutions using FIWARE, depending on which components and architecture³¹ are used:

- **Powered by FIWARE**
- **FIWARE ready**

The next sections explain in more detail which are the differences between concepts and how to identify them.

2.2.1 “Powered by FIWARE” solution/platform

The architecture of any "powered by FIWARE" solution/platform focuses on the management of context data through a Context Broker component, by using FIWARE NGSI as the core integration API. Smart solutions/platforms "powered by FIWARE" can easily integrate "FIWARE-ready" solutions following a "system of systems" approach as well as "FIWARE-ready" IoT devices and leverage the other open-source components found in the FIWARE Catalogue for rapid development.

Depending on which will be the final product there are two categories labelled “*powered by FIWARE*”:

- “Powered by FIWARE” Solution: A full end-to-end solution whose architecture focuses on management of context data through a context broker using FIWARE NGSI as core integration API. It may gather context data from quite heterogeneous sources and perform processing and visualization of context data to bring support to the smart automation of certain process and/or the adoption of smart decisions by end users.

³⁰ <https://docs.docker.com/get-started/overview/>

³¹ <https://fiware-marketplace.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

- “Powered by FIWARE” Platform: A software platform integrating a set of FIWARE components, and potentially other platform components, that supports the development and runtime execution of “Powered by FIWARE” solutions. A FIWARE-compliant Context Broker is the core component of any “Powered by FIWARE” platform and FIWARE NGSI is its core integration API. A “Powered by FIWARE” platform can be deployed on public/private clouds or at the premises of the platform users.

2.2.2 “FIWARE ready”

Solutions or devices which implement a FIWARE NSGI interface, but whose architecture is not “powered by FIWARE” are able to provide and consume context information. These are referred to as “FIWARE-ready”. The ability for a Solution or an IoT device to be “FIWARE-ready” can be developed via the use of intermediate services such as an IoT Agent, which can be used to translate proprietary message formats and transport protocols to NGSI. FIWARE provides open-source libraries for development of IoT Agents, as well as a portfolio of common IoT Agents, which can be used to translate from most popular IoT protocols to NGSI and vice-versa.

In summary, the ability for an IoT device to be “FIWARE-Ready” can be supplied either directly - with software on the device or indirectly - via the use of intermediate services, such as an IoT Agent, which can be used to translate proprietary message formats and transport protocols to NGSI.

Depending on which will be the final product, there are two categories labelled “powered by FIWARE”:

- “FIWARE-Ready” IoT Device: a concrete IoT device which is able to send and respond to messages using FIWARE NGSI, either natively or indirectly via the use of an IoT Agent, which can translate the native IoT message format and transport protocol, proprietary or not, supported by the device.
- “FIWARE-Ready” Solution: A software system whose architecture is not “Powered by FIWARE” but is able to exchange messages with a “Powered by FIWARE” solution/platform using FIWARE NGSI. Such systems may be full end-to-end solutions which can be integrated as part of a larger “Powered by FIWARE” solution following a “system of systems” approach. They may also be based on software platform components or enablers, which can be integrated as part of a “Powered by FIWARE” platform to extend its capabilities. “FIWARE-ready” solutions do not need to be open source.

2.3 B-WaterSmart interoperability maturity levels

In the context of the B-WaterSmart project, many tools are developed with different technologies and objectives and not all of them have or require the same level of interoperability. With the objective to provide a common framework to evaluate the interoperability maturity of any tool the concept of B-WaterSmart interoperability maturity levels has been created to allow the comparison among project tools and to provide a roadmap to evolve. This framework could be replicated easily to other environments vertical sectors or domains as it is only based on technical solutions to sustain

interoperability approaches. In this way, Figure 6 defines 5 levels of maturity in terms of interoperability focusing on the usage of standard data exchange solutions and the previously FIWARE maturity levels revised. It is important to say that lower maturity levels identify tools with less requirements and features to exchange data, when on the other side, the tools with higher maturity levels are tools using interoperable technologies that can easily exchange contextual information with other tools and they are based on FIWARE.

Figure 6 B-WaterSmart interoperability maturity levels

The definition of the levels has been elaborated according to the combination of different factors observed during the process done for tools analysis and explained in chapter 3 with the basis of the knowledge presented in chapters 4 and 5. The key points considered on the definition of the B-WaterSmart maturity levels are the following:

- **Interoperability requirements:** They are the basis to decide which maturity level we want to achieve. Tools that don't need or it has no sense for them to exchange data will require lower maturity levels. The need to exchange data in one way or bi-directionally, the privacy level on the data managed, the need to integrate external data sources, the need for contextual information about the origin of the data for data aggregation or processing, or the need to provide usable information to other tools are examples of interoperability requirements.

- **Availability and maturity of standard data models:** The data shared should be structured in common formats and with semantic contexts to facilitate its usage. The usage of ontologies, thesaurus, or the smart data models provided by FIWARE community are suitable solutions for interoperable data sharing. The selection of the particular solution will depend on the supporting technologies to transfer and store the data.
- **Availability and maturity of software components aiding in the software development:** The lack of interoperability based developing tools and frameworks (like FIWARE or ontology-based solutions), which at the same time usually require much more effort than alternative technical solutions available in the state of the art (not using standards or interoperability paradigms), is one of the reasons to not achieve fully interoperable solutions.
- **Available skills on interoperability:** There is a lack of experts on software development using interoperable solutions. Skipping the industrial sectors where standards are adopted to maximize profits, in other domains the lack of knowledge and dedicated training courses induce the lack technical professionals able to deal with these tasks.
- **Reliability and confidence on FIWARE:** FIWARE is a relatively novel community and set of technologies. Mainly early adopters, researchers or entrepreneurs are using them, but it needs to be demonstrated in more environments before being broadly adopted by the technical community
- **Ambition (Willingness/need) to be interoperable:** This point is highly dependent on previous ones but also on the strategy behind each business. As interoperability by design still is an utopia for many teams, interoperability related efforts must be justified in any tool design. There are tools that are based on data integration that would justify it easily specially if the data to integrate comes from heterogenous origins. On the other side legacy tools would need well endorsed business plans to justify interoperability investments that would mean changes on data models or architectures.

Finally, it is good to highlight the main differences between each level to allow its further usage. The following list tries to explain them adding some examples.

Level 0: Includes no interoperable tools, tools that doesn't need to exchange data with others, tools that cannot change data for instance due to privacy requirements.

Level 1: Includes tools includes technical solutions using standards or not to get data out of the tool to be used by others and at the same time consume data from external sources. This can be an example of a script consuming CSV data files or a web tool exporting the data into XLS format.

Level 2: Includes tools that use standard semantic data formats from other initiatives out of the FIWARE umbrella. This could be the case of any tool using industrial standards like MODBUS or ontologies like SAREF.

Level 3: Includes tools that are FIWARE compatible this means that they could exchange data with other tools powered by FIWARE and that they are exchanging data with contextual information using NGSI compatible data models.

Level 4: It includes only the tools powered by FIWARE components and the ones that are using NGSI-LD format for the data exchanged.

2.3.1 B-WaterSmart interoperability maturity level examples

This section collects a set of examples of tools showing the architecture and data workflow of each one, to guide any tool owner or developer on understanding the 5 interoperability maturity levels defined before. Each example (except the first one, due to the lack of data exchanging) is composed by 2 tools (tool #1 and tool #2) where tool #1 is the example representing the maturity level explained.

INTEROPERABILITY MATURITY LEVEL 0

The examples start with Level 0, which includes the tools with no interoperability. A simple example of architecture is presented in Figure 7 which could represent a simple web tool with a form to collect data. It is composed by a back-end to manage data and store it into a database. The front-end is composed by a dashboard presenting the data from the backend. The schema presents a standalone tool, without interaction with other software tools, so the data flows in a closed system.

Figure 7. Example of an interoperability maturity level 0 solution

INTEROPERABILITY MATURITY LEVEL 1

Figure 8. Example of an Interoperability Maturity Level 1 solution

The example shown in Figure 8 presents two tools that exchange data, so they are interoperable. Tool #2 can get data from tool #1 through a REST API. When Tool #2 makes a request to Tool #1, Tool #1 retrieves the data from a database and provides the information requested in JSON format. The structure of the data was decided unilaterally by Tool #1 developers according to their knowledge. In this example, the data structure is not standardized, so whoever wants to interact with Tool #1, must create a set of adaptors to transform its structure making it compatible with the data model of Tool #2.

INTEROPERABILITY MATURITY LEVEL 2

Figure 9. Example of an Interoperability Maturity Level 2 solution

In this case, Figure 9 shows the interoperability among both tools (#1 & #2) in a similar way to the previous example. However, there is a main difference. Here, SensorThings³² is used as a standard, giving semantic context to the data while in this case JSON is used as data interchange format. Additionally, there is a set of sensors storing data in a database, from where tool #1 will get the data in case tool #2 requests some information about the sensors through the API interface. The advantage of using standard structures is that any tool aiming to consume data from Tools like Tool #1 will not need to develop a new adaptor for every new tool to integrate and can integrate other sources of data easily by just configuring a new data origin. In the same way, as Tool#1 can be integrated easily by any customer familiar with the standard, it saves human resources for technical support from the Tool #1 team and simplifies the understanding of the data shared, increasing the potential of the data shared.

INTEROPERABILITY MATURITY LEVEL 3

Figure 10. Example of an Interoperability Maturity Level 3 solution

Level 3 is defined by the use of smart data models compatible with NGSI. Therefore, in the example presented in Figure 10, we have a “FIWARE ready” tool (Tool #1) and a “Powered by FIWARE” tool (Tool #2).

³² <https://www.ogc.org/standards/sensorthings>

Tool #1 doesn't make any use of FIWARE components of its catalogue. Thanks to a data conversion component, it can, however, exchange data with a "powered by FIWARE tool" (Tool#2, composed by FIWARE components) by using a client to communicate with its FIWARE context broker. In this way, Tool #1 can publish to a specific context element of Tool #2 and at the same time it can be subscribed to another context element. The data shared should be compliant with NGSI formats and the smart data models used.

The interoperability between the tools is possible thanks to the use of NGSI and smart data models that structure the data shared and including a data adaptor/transformation component (Data conversion module in the schema of Figure 10) as part of the tool. This adaptor transforms the data from the internal data model of Tool #1 to a compatible smart data model, thus enabling the communication with any other tool compatible with it. In our case this is Tool #2. Conversely, the adaptor transforms data received from Tool #2 from a smart data model to the internal data model. This example is very useful for those tools who want to be FIWARE compliant without refactoring their architecture from scratch. By adding an adaptor to the tool, it can share data with any FIWARE solution.

INTEROPERABILITY MATURITY LEVEL 4

Figure 11. Example of an Interoperability Maturity Level 4 solution

This schema describes the highest level of maturity in terms of interoperability through FIWARE. Both tools are “Powered by FIWARE” (they are composed by a “Context broker” from the FIWARE catalogue as main component) and make use of smart data models with JSON-LD as their format, so their APIs is NGSI-LD compatible. Internally, every tool could be composed by different components, depending on the requirements of each one. In this example we can see a few components of the FIWARE catalogue like:

- **IoT Agent:** it translates the native IoT message format and transport protocol.
- **Cygnus-LD:** the management of data and its injection into database.
- **Knowage:** as a Business Intelligence platform for data analysis and visualization.

It has to be emphasized that at least one component must be subscribed to the context broker, also in terms of interoperability with other tools.

Figure 11 shows an example of how two different tools could be interoperable and how the data can be managed by combining FIWARE components and non-FIWARE components like customized programs or external data sources. Obviously, this is a simple example, but the potential of a powered by FIWARE solution, is much bigger, as presented in chapter 4.

On the other hand, we must highlight the use of JSON-LD as a format for the data and NGSI-LD, which is able to manage this kind of data, allowing for associations between instances.

2.3.2 B-WaterSmart Tools maturity levels

In the B-WaterSmart project, a group of 22 software tools are being developed and improved. Some of these tools have adopted advanced interoperability approaches allowing FIWARE based communication between them. Some others do not follow this approach and focused on other objectives.

To provide a clear overview of the current interoperability maturity levels of these tools at the time of writing this document, Table 1 shows their maturity level according the evidences provided by the tool owners and reported in the column “Means of verification”.

Table 1. Interoperability Maturity level of B-WaterSmart tool grouped by Living Lab with explanation for this classification

Tool	Maturity level	Means of verification
VENICE		
#16-Water reuse strategic platform	4	Use of JSON-LD and NGSI-LD, use of Digital enabler as framework classified as Powered by FIWARE
#19-Sludge management platform	4	Use of JSON-LD and NGSI-LD, use of Digital enabler as framework classified as Powered by FIWARE tool
#32-Digital Enabler	4	Powered by FIWARE tool
LISBOA		

#17-Enviroment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action	1	Exchange of data through APIs not using standard data models
#24-Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model	1	Exchange of data through APIs not using standard data models
#25-Water-energy-P balance planning	1	Exchange of data through APIs not using standard data models
#27-Risk Assessment for Urban Water Reuse module	1	Exchange of data through APIs not using standard data models
#33-Climate-readiness Certification Tool	1	Exchange of data through APIs not using standard data models
#20-Urban Water Cycle Observatory Tool	1	Exchange of data through APIs not using standard data models
EAST FRISIA		
#22-Urban Water Optioneering Tool	1	Exchange of data through CSV / XML files
#23-Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS tool	1	Exchange of data through CSV / XML files
#28-Short-Term Demand Forecasting tool	1	Exchange of data capability through JSON files. <i>*Assessing the use of NGSI -> potential tool with IML 3</i>
FLANDERS		
#21-Stormwater Reuse Management System	1	Will get data through MQTT protocols, and JSON and CSV data from external APIS
#22-Urban Water Optioneering Tool	1	Exchange of data through CSV / XML files
#26-QMRA+	0	Reporting tool, not interoperable
#31-SuTRa	0	Not interoperable
Bodø		
#29-Nessie System	3	Is ready to get data from NGSI-LD, so its FIWARE compliant but not use FIWARE components

#30-Azure Cosmos DB and Environmental Dashboard	1	Exchange of data through APIs not using standard data models <i>*Assessing the usage of FIWARE components -> Potential IML 4</i>
ALICANTE		
#18-RE-ACTOR	0	No interoperable, output as web report and stored data
TRANSVERSAL (multi-site)		
#34-Water smartness assessment framework (WP6) and tool (T3.9)	4 (this is anticipated maturity level, the task 3.9 on dashboard development is to start in M25)	It will be powered by FIWARE components (according to the Tool Factsheet)

3 Tools analysis

3.1 Tool Factsheets'

We created a fact sheet template with a list of fields considered relevant to describe the functionalities of each tool to have complete and descriptive information about each tool and the context of its development. Table 2 gives an example of the fact sheet and a brief description for each field:

Table 2.- Tool Factsheet template

[Tool name] [#ID]	
Last update	Date of the last Update of the information collected of the tool on the fact sheet
General	<p>Reflected in GA: Indicates if the tool was previously reflected in the Grant Agreement (GA) grant agreement document. Some tool is not reflected, so we need to know if we can find initial information in the GA.</p> <p>Tool objective: What is the problem or the requirement that the tool is meant to solve or improve.</p> <p>Tool description: Description of the tool. What the tool can do.</p> <p>Tool owner: Company/Partner responsible for the tool.</p> <p>Tool contact: Name and e-mail of the responsible persons.</p> <p>Partners providing data: Which tools could be of interest for providing data.</p> <p>Partners consuming results: Which tools could be of interest for consuming data provided by this tool.</p>
Current context	<p>Domain: Is the category under the main topic (which in the case of B-WaterSmart is related to water) that the tool is addressed to. Such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scarcity • Distribution • Demand • Reuse • Quality • Resources availability <p>Use cases definition status: The first step to develop a tool is the definition of the challenges to be addressed. Once the challenges or use cases are defined the development of the tool can start. It's important to know the status of its definition.</p>

	<p>Domain Features: Which is the type of the values managed by the tool, or category of the values under the water management scope.</p> <p>Technical features: Components involved and their technical aspects like technology used (software and hardware), functional and non-functional requirements like interactions, connections, security, volume of data, etc.</p> <p>Users: Who will be the user of this tool? e.g. Municipalities, industry, particular users, householders, authorities, technology providers, etc...</p> <p>More information: Complementary information related to technical issues, definitions, next steps, delays, risks, impact, etc. that was not previously considered.</p>
Schedule	Schedule of the development: use cases, design, development, testing and plan of the completion
Input Data (type)	Type of data the tool needs to consume
Output Data (type)	Type of data the tool provides
Data models	Smart data models that better fit for the tool
Last update	Date of the last update of the fact sheet

This type of information was collected during the first period of the project, during which the tools were being updated and developed. The complete list of factsheets for all B-WaterSmart tools is included in **ANNEX A: B-WaterSmart Tool** .

3.2 Use cases per Living Lab

As described in previous sections, one of the first steps in any tool development is to define the use cases as the baseline to follow. The uses cases definition is a methodology used on software development to describe the features a tool should have and how they should be implemented³³. With the need to address this stage and provide the correct guidelines to all the tools, one of the first tasks has been to send a “*use case template*” created from Eurecat team based on their experience to all the tool owners to acquire this information. The template defined is composed by the following fields:

- **Id:** Every use case has a unique and identifiable ID, at least in its Living Lab.

³³ <https://www.usability.gov/how-to-and-tools/methods/use-cases.html>

- **Use case description D:** describes the purpose of the use case.
- **Component:** Name of the component inside the tool in charge of carrying out this action.
- **Goal:** Objective of the use case, or the aim to develop this action.
- **Pre-conditions:** Context of the tool (system context or data) before the execution.
- **Triggers:** It is the action/desire/event that fires the need to execute/address this use case. An event or situation, etc. that causes something to start.
- **Post-conditions:** Context of the tool (system context or data) after the execution.
- **Actor:** Tool component, user profile or user role who triggers the action or is able to do the action
- **Steps:** Steps followed by the system or user that makes the tool respond with the expected result.
- **Notes:** Clarifications or extra information not portrayed in previous fields
- **Comments:** Space to provide feedback and improvement

This kind of information is defined on the initial steps of the project. It is an important step to define the requirements and with it, the way to follow in terms of development, actions, functions, features, components, etc. The complete list of use cases for all B-WaterSmart tools is included in **ANNEX B: Tools use cases**.

3.3 Technical requirements

Thanks to the information collected on the previous sections (see Section (3.1 and 3.2), we can broadly define the initial interoperability requirements of each tool that will be fine-tuned during the project. However, at this stage, they can be used to confirm initial design of the architectures, to make some changes on them if needed and to have a better overview about the data models to use and assess which to use. Indeed, the requirements could be useful for any other development team as examples for their projects.

The Table 3 shows descriptive technical information about each tool after analysing several sources of information given by tool owners: The tool fact sheets, the use cases and updates reported on WP2-WP3 meetings. After that, for each tool its business objectives are reported, as well as the main user capabilities. Moreover, the tables include along with a list of requirements (functional and non-functional). Finally, a brief description of the type of tool is also added. When some information about the tool has not been informed for any reason by the Tool owners, it is just specified as “Not reported”

Table 3. Summary of tool requirements grouped per Living lab

Tool	Requirements
VENICE	
#16-Water reuse strategic platform	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sewage sludge valorization • Rank the best treatments for the sludge <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User can log in • Introduce quality of water

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Territory selection • Territory data visualization • Topics selection (territory, resources, destination/use, regulations) <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide outputs using NGS-LD and JSON-LD • Can collect Geotiff metadata • Read information (inputs) from CSV files • Use of “water quality” data model from smart data model initiative • Provide maps, charts and tables based on input information <p>Non-functional requirements: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation: Dashboard as web application and backend integrating and storing data</p>
#19-Sludge management platform	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rank reuse opportunities of water for preserving fresh water. • Mitigate effects in terms of requirements and infrastructure needs, geographical, political, and regulatory issues <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User can log in • Introduce quality of water • Territory selection • Territory data visualization • Topics selection (territory, resources, destination/use, regulations) <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide outputs in JSON-LD format in NGS-LD • Can collect Geotiff metadata • Read information (inputs) from CSV files • Provide maps, charts and tables based on input information <p>Non-functional requirements: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation: Dashboard as web application and backend integrating and storing data</p>
#32-Digital Enabler	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help with real time data management: visualization, integration, storage <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depend on the application that uses it <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context broker able to receive and provide real time data using NGS-LD formats • Storage of semantic data • Visualization of data <p>Non-functional requirements: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation: Middleware based on FIWARE components</p>
LISBOA	
#17-Environment	Business/objective:

<p>for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multi-criteria decision tool to compare and decide alternative demand/supply matches based on analytics <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities: Not reported</p> <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To show data numerically and graphically on geo referenced 2D/3D cityscape environment Uses online data sources Getting and providing data from external and other sources Own data model shared with #25 and #27 Ability to read any format Output is a supply/demand combination <p>Non-functional req.: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation: Not reported</p>
<p>#24-Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model</p>	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantify risk distribution Modelling hydraulic and water quality of reclaimed water <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities: Not reported</p> <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Getting data from sensors (e.g., chlorine residuals, temperature, turbidity, pH) in EPANET format about hydraulic/water quality Output data exportable to EPANET, so the same EPANET format about hydraulic/water quality and model results pertaining to the reclaimed water formulation utilized <p>Non-functional req.: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation: Not reported</p>
<p>#25-Water-energy-P balance planning</p>	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design of demand/supply alternatives including availability, cost, energy and nutrients <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities: Not reported</p> <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EPANET standard hydraulic model Input data are time-series about flow, cost, energy values, nutrients Output data is a specific data model (self-developed) including data about: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water volume / energy / nutrient balances Including time and geographical units <p>Non-functional req.: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation: Not reported</p>
<p>#27-Risk Assessment for Urban Water Reuse module</p>	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess supply/demand combination for risk, based on EU regulation and ISO standards to facilitate health and environmental risk assessment and management of water reuse. Pass/Fail status of supply/demand alternative assessed <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities: Not reported</p> <p>Functional requirements:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EPANET standard hydraulic model • Input data is time-series about flow, cost, energy values, nutrient values • Output results is a 2D/3D environment with indicators of risk per timestamp using specific data model. <p>Non-functional req.: Not reported Implementation: Not reported</p>
<p>#33-Climate-readiness Certification Tool</p>	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To provide water-smart for climate ready's building certificates (CRC) • Output with the qualitative result of water and energy efficiency from the water uses and the suitability of the water uses to the climate context, applied to households, buildings, and neighborhoods <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities: Not reported</p> <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input data about location of buildings, characteristics, and equipment (water deposits, irrigation equipment; pools, with the associated treatment equipment, taps and showers, elevation or recirculation pumps, water treatment equipment, toilet flushes, sinks and bathtubs, water network, hot water production equipment), data from smart meters • Output data, efficiency certificates with geographical information <p>Non-functional req.: Not reported Implementation: Not reported</p>
<p>#20-Urban Water Cycle Observatory Tool</p>	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To inform about the water and wastewater dimensions in terms of consumption and costs <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users visualize data of water and wastewater of Lisbon city • Login • Select water or wastewater in public access • Customize visualization selecting total or per capital data • Customize visualization selecting specific information • Visualize historical data consumption/cost per type of use • Water meter selection • Area selection for water meters visualization map • Filter options on water meters visualization • Definition of alerts like leakages and overconsumption <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Output information about historical data presented in graphs (possibility to download graphs) • Analysis of water consumption on selected data frames • Automatic performance reports of previous analysis in PDF format • Get data from #17 and #25 to confirm

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Getting data from water supplier of Lisbon • Share data through REST API • Output data formats: CSV, XLS, PDF, PNG • Evaluating data ingestion via API from Water Supplier of Lisbon <p>Non-functional req.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management of public and private access from/to data sources <p>Implementation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website tool
EAST FRISIA	
<p>#22-Urban Water Optioneering Tool</p>	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through a model-based system, forecast available water quality and quantity under climatic change conditions. • Simulate feasibility of water solutions <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Login • Add components to design network water system • Enter new data • Run simulation • Visualize output data • Export output data <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input data is open data and technical parameters from stakeholders. • Input data format CSV files of timeseries of quantitative parameters (flow, rainfall, fluctuation) • Getting input data through txt files or excel files, and a Hydrologic software • Output data in CSV files of timeseries and XML file from the model <p>Non-functional req.: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation: Stand-alone tool</p>
<p>#23-Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS tool</p>	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify water requirements and match these with available resources, if necessary, calculating transport and treatment • Store meta-data <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Login • Define map scale • Add data information on data base <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inputs from sensors, weather stations and web services • Output is datasets of water resources and water demand location and time <p>Non-functional req.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated with #22-UWOT <p>Implementation:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R-statistics • FREEWAT (addon for QGIS)
#28-Short-Term Demand Forecasting tool	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water demand forecasting and allocation of water resources based on modelling techniques, smart data meters and weather data. <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Login • Define areas to make predictions from menu • Add sub-areas • Enter information of sub-area (Name, num. of residents, socio-economic information, location, associated smart meters) • Choose algorithm • Train model • Visualize historical smart data meters • Select time frame for smart data meters <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input of historical data in JSON format from water-meters, and time series of water consumption and weather prediction. • Output data is the same format and type of input but for predictions • Show evaluation scores made by the model and an overview of the assumptions made and data used • Show line plots of historical data of smart data meters <p>Non-functional req.: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web tool
FLANDERS	
#21-Stormwater Reuse Management System	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unblocking the water reuse potential of rainwater infrastructure through real-time control. <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Login • Visualize data of water level tank and soil moisture • Activate/Deactivate irrigation • Visualize used volume of water • Visualize water volume available for future irrigation • Open/Close tank sluice if threshold is exceeded <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input data queried through existing APIs using available data formats like JSON and CSV. • Internal communication handled by MQTT protocol (publish/subscribe) <p>Non-functional req.: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation:</p> <p>Is a full-scale test environment for the optimisation of an integrated system</p>

	<p>composed of stormwater control and subirrigation</p>
<p>#22-Urban Water Optioneering Tool</p>	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To forecast available water quality and quantity under climatic change conditions through a model-based system. • Simulate feasibility of water solutions <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Login • Add components to design network water system • Enter new data • Run simulation • Visualize output data • Export output data <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input data is open data and technical parameters from stakeholders. • Input data format CSV files of timeseries of quantitative parameters (flow, rainfall, fluctuation) • Getting input data through txt files or excel files, and a Hydrologic software • Output data in CSV files of timeseries and XML file from the model <p>Non-functional req.: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation: Not reported</p>
<p>#26-QMRA+</p>	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obtain microbial risk assessment for water reuse <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Select data from reference database with generic information like: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Source of water ○ Treatment applied ○ Use of the water <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide report or table with the level of risk <p>Non-functional req.: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation: Web application</p>
<p>#31-SuTRa</p>	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predict microbial safety <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide data <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input data like: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Transport properties <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Distance ▪ Time ○ Aquifer properties <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Zone

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Grain size ○ Pathogen type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Name ▪ Concentration • Output data like: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Pathogen properties: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Size ▪ Stickiness ○ Output concentration <p>Non-functional req.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python package • Coupled with existing tools like #22-UWOT <p>Implementation: Library</p>
BODØ	
#29-Nessie System	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-house information system for monitoring of water consumption at household and network levels and remote control of sewer mining units, management of subsurface water systems, operational management of raw-water supply. <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection of water meters or households • Selection of time window • Visualization of data requested <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytics capability to identify leakages or bursts • Display (or send via e-mail) warnings when identifies leakages or bursts • FIWARE compliant tool • Get data from sensors through IoT agents • User-friendly interface, which allows quick manipulation and visualization of measurements and outcomes from 3rd party tools, models, and analytics • Display real-time information • Display forecasts on domestic water demand • Integrate different data-sources through an API • Input CSV type files with time series measurements of sensors (water quality, flow, pressure, temperature) • Input JSON type files with sensors and system characteristics, and outputs from external tools via API • Outputs in CSV file formats and JSON files through API <p>Non-functional req.: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation: Web application</p>
#30-Azure Cosmos DB and	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring the current state of the water network in home buildings

Environmental Dashboard	<p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Login • Select data category • Filter data • Visualize data • Geographical overview selection • Selection of type of data to be displayed in the map <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input data basically in JSON format, and also in CSV and XML • Communication protocol through REST API • Store data in relational database • Load data of category selected by user • Load section of different actions to play with the loaded data • Display data in a map <p>Non-functional req.: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation: Web application</p>
ALICANTE	
#18-RE-ACTOR	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate the evaluation of impacts in scenarios of new assets or their improvement for the reclaimed water system. <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Login • Select existing project • Select data category • Filter data • Visualize data • Geographical overview selection • Selection of type of data to be displayed in the map • Edit/add properties of assets • Create different scenarios • Select scenarios to compare • Choose the best scenario <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Display map, assets and current KPIs • Input data introduced by user via web forms (JSON format) • Input data regarding to the current/future scenario assets: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ type (WWTP, pond, renewable energy, etc) ○ location (GIS) ○ properties (m² installed, m³ produced, etc) • Store data in a relational DB • Output data as web report via PDF of following information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Environmental impact <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Carbon footprint ▪ Water footprint

#34-Water smartness assessment framework (WP6) and tool (T3.9)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Eutrophication of discharges ○ Economic impact <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CAPEX ▪ OPEX ▪ Return of investment ▪ Avoided costs <p>Non-functional req.: Accessibility constrained, users have access to specific projects</p> <p>Implementation: Web application</p>
TRANSVERSAL (multi-site)	
#34-Water smartness assessment framework (WP6) and tool (T3.9)	<p>Business/objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Framework <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Measure “water smartness gains” by analyzing user organization performance currently and in the future towards the achievement of set strategic achievements ○ Supports specific strategies towards a water-smart society based on the objectives defined <p>User/Stakeholder capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Login • Select criteria and metrics for the strategic objective • Visualize assessment of the water smartness of the framework • Visualize assessment of the water smartness of the framework at different dates • Export data output to excel • Access information material on need • Access feedback forms • Provide feedback manually using forms <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Powered by FIWARE dashboard • Dashboard receive data from framework <p>Non-functional req.: Not reported</p> <p>Implementation: Web application</p>

3.3.1 Data interoperability among B-WATERSMART tools

In this section the Table 4 shows the linkages between the project tools.

Table 4. Description of interoperability among B-WATERSMART Tools

Tool	Links	Data domains
VENICE		
#16-Water reuse strategic platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses components of #32 	Sewage treatments, water quality, geospatial

		data, policies
#19-Sludge management platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses components of #32 	Water reuse, water quality, geospatial data, policies
#32-Digital Enabler	Used by tools #16 & #19	Non-dependent on domain data
LISBOA		
#17-Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input data from #25 and #27 • Output data to #20 	Water demand, water supply, geospatial data
#24-Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input data from #25 • Output data to #27 	Risk, hydraulic models, water quality
#25-Water-energy-P balance planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Output data to #17 and 24 • Exchange data with #20 	Hydraulic models, energy and cost, water volumes
#27-Risk Assessment for Urban Water Reuse module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Output data to #17 and 24 • Exchange data with #20 	Risk, water reuse, hydraulic model, water flows
#33-Climate-readiness Certification Tool	No interoperable with other B-WaterSmart tools, only with internal tools: #33.1-Energy Efficiency Certificates and #33.2-AQUA+	Energy efficiency, water consumption, smart meters, certificates
#20-Urban Water Cycle Observatory Tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input data from #17 • Exchange data with #25 	Water consumption, wastewater management, infrastructure planning
EAST FRISIA		
#22-Urban Water Optioneering Tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange data with #28 • Extended as part of #23, from where will get data 	Water quality, simulation, hydraulic models
#23-Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange data with #28 • Output data to #22 	Water demand, water supply, costs, water treatment, geospatial data
#28-Short-Term Demand Forecasting tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange data with #22 and #23 	Water demand, water supply, water meters, weather data
FLANDERS		
#21-Stormwater Reuse	No specifications of interoperability	Water scarcity, water

Management System		reuse
#22-Urban Water Optioneering Tool	Exchange data with #21, potential interoperability with #26, #31 (will be assessed during modelling)	Water simulation, quality, hydraulic models
#26-QMRA+	Reporting tool, no interoperability reported	Water reuse, risk assessment
#31-SuTRa	Complying with existing tools like #22-UWOT, but not interoperable tool	Risk assessment
BODØ		
#29-Nessie System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exchange data with #30 	Water management, water quality, wastewater
#30-Azure Cosmos DB and Environmental Dashboard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exchange data with #29 	Water network, water management, water meters
ALICANTE		
#18-RE-ACTOR	Not interoperable specifications	Water demand, water scarcity, KPIs, wastewater
TRANSVERSAL (multi-site)		
#34-Water smartness assessment framework (WP6) and tool (T3.9)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To be defined during the second part of the project. 	KPIs

4 B-WaterSmart FIWARE-base Reference Architecture

4.1 FIWARE4WATER reference architecture

In this section we present the work conducted in the framework of EU-funded Fiware4Water project (2019-2022) (Fiware4Water, 2021) for the raw-water supply system that serves the city of Athens (Greece) as an indicative recently developed FIWARE-enabled solution for the water sector. The system is characterized by high complexity and large extent, comprising an extensive system of aqueducts of total length 495 km, a large number of structures that regulate flow (stilling basins for energy dissipation and hydro-power stations for energy productions). The monitoring, management and control of the system is achieved via an extensive network of water quantity and quality sensors composed by 5 open channel flowmeters, more than 10 close-pipe flow meters, more than 50 open channel water level meters and 12 water quality meters measuring water turbidity, conductivity, temperature. This network has been expanded over the years to include sensors installed from different vendors, leading to the development of independent proprietary information systems that co-exist within the water utility (named EYDAP) that operates the system.

In light of the above challenges, the integration of different legacy systems (i.e., sensors, data streams, data management and visualization platforms, algorithms) of such a complex raw-water system into a single digital solution with interoperable and portable capabilities is of high importance for the optimal management and operation of the system. To accomplish this, a FIWARE-enabled system reference architecture has been designed. This system reference architecture integrates data and analytics, using FIWARE protocols and components (Kossieris, 2021).

A schematic overview of the system architecture is given in Figure 12, presenting the underlying mechanisms for data transport and manipulation, along with FIWARE modules. The yellow area in Figure 12 corresponds to the Data Warehouse of EYDAP which integrates data from different data sources and sensors. To establish communication with the Data Warehouse of EYDAP an FTP server, a database schema, and a scheduler (File Storage/Main File System area in the graph) are configured to feed the “CSV IoT Agent”. The “CSV IoT Agent” (upper middle box) retrieves the files from the FTP Server on a timely fashion and converts them into NGSI-LD requests for the ORION-LD Context Broker (CB), which lies in the heart of any FIWARE-enabled architecture. The ORION-LD CB has been configured with the static information of the sensors of the study area, following the relevant NGSI-LD data models. Orion-LD uses a subscription-based system to notify external real-time applications, depicted on the left side of the architecture diagram (magenta area).

To certify data persistency, Draco module, which is based on Apache NiFi, is used. Draco is notified when new data becomes available in ORION-LD CB, inserting them using SQL queries to the PostgreSQL/PostGIS Database Server (see the second middlebox). Draco distributes data through simple HTTP POST requests to the PostgreSQL/PostGIS database. NiFi is a dataflow system which supports powerful and scalable directed graphs of data routing. It automates the flow of data between systems. In our case it automates the flow of data between the ORION-LD CB and the PostgreSQL database for storing them persistently. Since the PostgreSQL database is a simple RDBMS and not a Server that accepts HTTP requests (in our case, sent by Draco), an intermediate HTTP server interface is currently being built to receive the HTTP requests from Draco and convert them into SQL queries.

NESSIE (NTUA/ICCS in-house developed Web Server and Data Analysis & Archiving Engine) retrieves on real-time basis timestamped data from the Context Broker after subscribing, while in cases where historical data are required, NESSIE retrieves data from the PostgreSQL database server (see third middle box). NESSIE also provides the necessary tools to analyse historical and real-time data, supporting their display into user defined dashboards using a modern asynchronous web interface.

To support a fast and robust big-data data processing in real-time, the “Apache Spark” module is also included in the platform architecture. This module provides high-level APIs in Java, Scala, Python and R, and an optimized engine that supports general execution graphs. It also supports a rich set of higher-level tools including Spark SQL for SQL and structured data processing, MLlib for machine learning, GraphX for graph processing, and Structured Streaming for incremental computation and stream processing. Apache Spark module executes the necessary big-data processing operations and pushes the results back to Orion Context Broker (via *Cosmos Big Data Generic Enabler*) so as for registered 3rd party applications to be notified.

Figure 12 Overview of the FIWARE-enabled system architecture for Athens demo case in the framework of Fiware4Water.

4.2 B-WATERSMART reference architecture

The wide variety of interoperability requirements/objectives and the great heterogeneity of smart-water readiness that characterize the organizations that operate in the water industry are key drivers for conceiving a reference architecture for allowing seamless data flows among them. As seen in section 1.5.3, FIWARE, and in particular the Context Broker, can be used at different levels to integrate systems and services.

But, the Context Broker, together with the other FIWARE GE mentioned above, is part of a broad Reference Architecture that can be easily deployed in the Smart Water domain. As shown in the figure below, developed in the context of the ICT4Water cluster (<https://ict4water.eu>), the FIWARE Context Broker can be leveraged by instantiating Data Models from the Smart Data Model Initiative and in particular those related to the Smart Water category. B-WaterSmart will provide some specific contribution by defining new data models or by extending data models that are already available.

The FIWARE Context Broker and its data models will be fed by dedicated System Adapters and IoT Agent, depending on the type of data source (e.g., EPANET, weather services, vertical systems, IoT networks, smart devices), and will make available context data to other components and services, both inside and outside the organization. For example, data can be made available to Smart Water Management Services (e.g., Big Data or AI applications, dashboards for data visualization and KPI evaluation, GIS applications). This can be done directly or after an intermediate processing done by dedicated engines (e.g. Spark, Flink) or by software applications like dashboard management systems, GIS or data mashup tools. Moreover, following the paradigm of Data Spaces, data can be made available to third party organizations, both by federating respective Context Brokers or by publishing the data through a Data Marketplace with full support to data monetization or through an Open data portal. In any case, this will require appropriate security and privacy measures by adopting dedicated Identity Management and Control systems and procedures.

Figure 13 FIWARE Reference Architecture for the Smart Water domain (ICT4Water)

5 B-WaterSmart Proposed Data solutions

This chapter describes the data solutions relevant for the tools developed in the B-WaterSmart project in terms of data models, ontologies, and interface specifications. It further compares different alternative setups whenever FIWARE is implemented.

5.1 Existing data models and ontologies for water domain tools

5.1.1 State of the art

As a result of the increase of smart systems that are being developed for the water domain, many of the already existing standardization initiatives have expanded their efforts to the water area. Data standardization is crucial when data originating from different sources and providers is to become part of common services within a utility or between diverse utilities. The goal of the data standards and corresponding data models is to enable the exchange of such data between information systems. As pointed out by (Makropoulos & Savić, 2019), the standardization of the water domain usually comes as an extension of efforts started in other domains. In this section, some recent examples of such significant efforts and the corresponding data models for the water domain are briefly described. Some of the data models discussed in this section can be found also at initiative from NAIADES project, that gathers existing water standards ³⁴.

Water ML is a domain specific standard data model created by Open Geospatial Consortium. It is used for representing water observation data. It consists of four parts, focusing respectively on i) time series, ii) Ratings, Gaugings and Sections, iii) surface hydrology features, iv) ground water. Saref4watr ontology (Etsi, 2020) belongs to the SAREF (Smart Appliances REFerence ontology) family of standards developed by European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) (Etsi, 2020). Smart Data Models is a collaborative initiative launched by FIWARE Foundation, TMForum, and IUDX. The initiative makes agile standardized free and open-licensed data models available. The models are based on real cases and open standards. They are compliant with FIWARE NGSI V2 and NGSI-LD used for context information. The Smart Data Models Initiative provides data models for diverse sectors that are grouped into thematic domains e.g Smart Cities, Smart Agrifood, Smart Smart Energy, Smart Sensing and others. Smart Water is a separate domain for smart data models associated with water management. This domain at the time of writing this Deliverable (April 2021) contains 6 subjects: Water Network Management EPANET, Water Consumption, Water Quality, Water Distribution, Open Channel Management and Waste Water Additionally, there is a group of cross-sectoral data models that are related to more than one domains (e.g. Key performance indicator, weather, etc.) Some of the Smart Data Models belonging to Smart Water domain and cross-sectoral data models will be discussed in more detail in the context of BWS tools in the Section 5.3 on B-WaterSmart proposed data solutions per tool. Those data models could be potentially used as part of BWS interoperability solutions wherever suitable supporting the interoperability through exposing data through data models. An initial analysis of the input and output

³⁴ <https://aolite.github.io/naiadesStandardization/#/standards>

data of BWS tools was performed to identify links to existing smart data models and the input/output data possible relations between the tools.

5.1.2 Smart Data Models (FIWARE data models)

Smart data models initiative is a joint collaboration between FIWARE Foundation, TM Forum, and IUDX to support the adoption of a reference architecture and compatible common data models that underpin a digital market of interoperable and replicable smart solutions in multiple sectors, starting with Smart Cities.³⁵

A smart data model includes three elements: The schema, or technical representation of the model defining the technical data types and structure, the specification of a written document for human readers, and the examples of the payloads for NGSIv2 and NGSI-LD versions.

Smart data models initiative is continuously being expanded with new data models to a wide range of sectors. Currently, various data models are available for Smart Cities, Environment, Aeronautics, Agrifood, Robotics, Destination, Sensing, Health, Energy, Manufacturing and Water at <https://github.com/smart-data-models/SmartWater>. Under the water sector, the Smart Water Data Models initiative is supported by the ICT4Water cluster in the adoption of reference architectures and also common naming conventions of data exchange between water data.

Focusing especially on the water sector, 3 categories of data models are available covering different aspects of water cycle. Specifically, these categories concern:

- Raw-water (open-channel) conveyance systems
- Drinking water distribution networks
- Waste-water treatment plants

Each of the above categories comprises specific Entities, that define physical or conceptual (virtual) objects uniquely identified by a URI (Uniform Resource Identifier) that consist of the Entity Id. An Entity has properties that are the static or dynamic intrinsic characteristics of an Entity (e.g., a GeoProperty which describes the geospatial information of the Entity), receiving values, which can be a single value (number, Boolean or DateTime) or complex value (array or any kind of structured data). Furthermore, an entity has relationships which are URIs pointing to another entity. According to NGSI-LD specifications, a property can also have properties and relationships with other entities. Accordingly, a relationship may have properties and relationships with other entities.

Raw-water (open-channel) conveyance system

This category includes data models for the key physical components and water-related structures that can be found in an open-channel system. Specifically, the following entity types are available:³⁶

OpenChannel. This entity contains a harmonised description of a generic channel. It allows the definition of the characteristics and geometry of the channel (e.g., length, type of geometry, side

³⁵ <https://www.fiware.org/developers/smart-data-models/>

³⁶ <https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.OpenChannelManagement/tree/4f0b344719f6441d90d7d9b6f8c4fb8e7d1dad7a>

slopes, bottom width, bottom slope, maximum allowable water depths etc.) as well as hydraulic parameters (e.g., Manning's roughness coefficient). It also includes relationships to support the formulation of the topology of a system, such as the downstream and upstream node.

OpenChannelJunction. This entity contains a harmonised description of a generic Junction. A Junction defines a location where the characteristics of the channel changes, two or more channels come together or split apart, amounts of water are abstracted or inserted to the system etc.

CrossSection. This entity contains a harmonised description of a generic cross-section, which defines any point of the system where raw-water properties are monitored by a device and/or computed via simulation. It can be attached to a channel to provide a more detailed representation of its geometric characteristics via the relevant properties.

SluiceGate. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic sluice gate. It describes both the geometric characteristics of the gate (e.g., gate width, height, bottom elevation etc.) as well as the hydraulic characteristics of the flow (e.g., discharge and orifice coefficients to account for energy losses, water flow, energy difference etc.). To support the modelling of flow through sluice gates, 4 relationships have been defined to allow connection with CrossSection entities, upstream and downstream to the sluice gate, which serve as control points in a distance and near the sluice gates.

Spillway. This entity contains a harmonized description for a generic Spillway, which represents a junction-type object, controlling the release of water from a dam or regulation structure downstream. The model allows the definition of the geometric characteristics (e.g., crest elevation, length, width) of different types of spillways, such as the *Broad-Crested*, *Ogee* and *Sharp-Crested* spillway. Hydraulic characteristics (e.g., discharge coefficient) and design properties (e.g., design discharge, maximum flood elevation etc.) have also been defined. To support the modelling of flow over spillway, the *controlCrossSection* relationship has been inserted to allow the connection with a *CrossSection* entity, serving as control point of the spillway.

RegulationStructure. This entity contains a harmonised description of a generic Regulation Structure, which represents a junction-type object, controlling the water flow in the raw-water system. It allows the description of more complicated structures that regulate flow in a channel, composed by both regulation structures and spillways.

OpenChannelSystem. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic raw-water (open channel) system. This entity represents either a system composed of different components (e.g., channels, junctions, cross-sections etc.) or just a component (e.g., a SluiceGate).

In addition to the above entities, representing physical components of a raw-water (open-channel) system, two additional data models are available to serve modelling applications. These are:

OpenChannelFlowRegulation. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic simulation of a series of independent regulation structures to establish specific flow conditions in the conveyance system.

RegulationStructureSimulation. This entity contains a harmonized description of a data model for the combined modelling of a set of regulation structures.

Indicatively, next figure provides a schematic representation of the *OpenChannel* entity along with its properties (yellow ellipse) and relationships (rhombus).

Figure 14 Schematic representation of the *OpenChannel* entity, including its properties (yellow ellipse) and relationships with other entities (rhombus).

Drinking water distribution networks

This category includes data models for the key components of a drinking water distribution network. Specifically, the following entity types are available, following the key components of EPANET model:³⁷

Pipe. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic pipe.

Junction. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic junction.

Tank. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic tank.

Valve. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic valve.

Pump. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic pump.

Reservoir. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic reservoir.

Network. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic network.

Pattern. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic pattern.

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<https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.WaterDistributionManagementEPANET/tree/9f9d6a8bcd06a96a5f5967091e8bef74024fb6e5>

Simulation Scenario. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic simulation scenario.

Simulation Result. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic simulation result.

Waste-water treatment plants

This category includes data models for the key components of a waste-water treatment plants. Specifically, the following entity types are available:³⁸

Blower. This entity contains a harmonized description of a Blower. The entity represents a Blower that is used for aeration purposes in the wastewater treatment process. Important parameters are measured to regulate and measure the amount of airflow is being provided to the aeration tank in the bioreactor. Energy consumption of a blower is also important information for real-time control and optimization of the wastewater treatment plant.

OffGasStack. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic Off-gas Stack. This entity represents stacks that are present in some wastewater treatment plants where the emissions, greenhouse gases included, are emitted.

WasteWaterJunction. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic Junction. Junctions could be in place in certain sections of the treatment plant. In wastewater treatment purposes, the junction is most useful if it is a location of a sensor that measures a specific variable.

WasteWaterSimulationResult. This entity contains a harmonized description of a WasteWaterSimulationResults. The entity contains properties that are parameters which have been predicted or forecasted by models through a simulation.

WasteWaterTank. This entity contains a harmonized description of a generic Tank. For a given type of tank, all possible variables that can be measures are listed as properties. In the description property, the type of tank (anaerobic, pre-denitrification, nitrification etc.) can be defined.

Water Consumption

This category³⁹ includes data models to capture water consumption, customer side alarms and associated flow rate originating from the smart meters. The key entity “WaterConsumptionObserved” provides the following properties:

alarmFlowPersistence: Alarm signifying continuous water use

alarmInProgress: Indicates that one or more alarms are in progress

alarmStopsLeaks: Alarm signifying the potential for an intermittent leak

alarmTamper: Alarm signifying the potential of mechanical tampering with the device

alarmWaterQuality: Alarm signifying the potential of backflows occurring

³⁸

<https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.WasteWater/tree/19e42b511b63ff204b80e7cdc6b010739758552e>

³⁹

<https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.WaterConsumption/tree/1e34f95195dcfa921945b2a92d061931d66c3aba>

alternateName: An alternative name for this item

areaServed: The geographic area where a service or offered item is provided

dataProvider: A sequence of characters identifying the provider of the harmonised data entity.

maxFlow: Maximum flow rate observed during the last week

minFlow: Minimum flow rate observed during the last week

moduleTampered: Removal of module from metering device

persistenceFlowDuration: The duration for which persistence flow (continuous flow) is recorded by the meter. The text field shows durations in minutes (m), hours (h) or days (d).

waterConsumption: The water meter reading. Note – this is total volume passed through the meter and is therefore a cumulative total at the time

Water Quality

This category includes data models to represent water quality parameters at a certain water mass (river, lake, sea, etc.) section. The key entity “WaterQualityObserved” provides the following properties⁴⁰:

Chla: Concentration of chlorophyll A.

Cl-: Concentration of chlorides.

NH3: Concentration of ammonia.

NH4: Concentration of ammonium.

NO3: Concentration of nitrates.

O2: Level of free, non-compound oxygen present.

PC: Concentration of pigment phycocyanin which can be measured to estimate cyanobacteria concentrations specifically.

PE: Concentration of pigment phycoerythrin which can be measured to estimate cyanobacteria concentrations specifically.

PO4: Concentration of phosphates.

address: The mailing address

alternateName: An alternative name for this item

areaServed: The geographic area where a service or offered item is provided

bod: Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) is the amount of dissolved oxygen (DO) needed (i.e. demanded) by aerobic biological organisms to break down organic material present in a given water sample at certain temperature over a specific time period

⁴⁰

<https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.WaterQuality/tree/de6371e975d2c73b7d4b0d077daaf7adb9fa78ca/WaterQualityObserved>

cod: Chemical oxygen demand (COD) is an indicative measure of the amount of oxygen that can be consumed by reactions in a measured solution

conductance: Specific Conductance.

conductivity: Electrical Conductivity.

dataProvider: A sequence of characters identifying the provider of the harmonized data entity.

dateCreated: Entity creation timestamp. This will usually be allocated by the storage platform.

dateModified: Timestamp of the last modification of the entity. This will usually be allocated by the storage platform.

dateObserved: The date and time of this observation in ISO8601 UTC format. It can be represented by a specific time instant or by an ISO8601 interval.

description: A description of this item

id: Unique identifier of the entity

location: Geojson reference to the item. It can be Point, LineString, Polygon, MultiPoint, MultiLineString or MultiPolygon

measurand: An array of strings containing details (see format below) about extra measures provided by this observation.

name: The name of this item.

orp: Oxidation-Reduction potential.

owner: A List containing a JSON encoded sequence of characters referencing the unique Ids of the owner(s)

pH: Acidity or basicity of an aqueous solution.

refPointOfInterest: A reference to a point of interest associated to this observation.

salinity: Amount of salts dissolved in water.

seeAlso: list of uri pointing to additional resources about the item

source: A sequence of characters giving the original source of the entity data as a URL. Recommended to be the fully qualified domain name of the source provider, or the URL to the source object.

tds: Total dissolved solids.

temperature: Temperature

tss: Total suspended solids.

turbidity: Amount of light scattered by particles in the water column

type: NGSi Entity type. It has to be WaterQualityObserved

Cross-sector data models⁴¹

In addition to the above described purely water-related smart data models, a series cross-sector data models, which can be found useful and relevant to water applications, are available:

- **keyPerformanceIndicator:** A Key Performance Indicator (KPI) is a type of performance measurement. KPIs evaluate the success of an organization or of a particular activity in which it engages.
- **PointOfInterest:** This entity contains a harmonized geographic description of a Point of Interest
- **RiskManagement:** This category contains data models which are useful for the Risk Assessment representation inside a water critical infrastructure, considering the modelling of cascading effects. The entities that are available are: Asset, CyberAnalysis, Exposure, GISData, Hazard, Measure, Mitigation, NetworkServiceAlert, Risk, Vulnerability.
- **Weather:** These data models describe entities useful for dealing with weather data. The entities that are available are: WaetherAlert, WeatherForecast and WeatherObserved
-

5.1.3 SAREF Ontologies

This section will include a description of the SAREF ontologies⁴² that are considered relevant in B-WaterSmart. The overview provided in Table 5 describes some statistics for these ontologies.

Table 5. Ontology statistics for relevant SAREF ontologies

SAREF Module	Ontology	Number of classes	Number of object properties	Number of data properties
SAREF Core		81	35	5
SAREF4WATR		72	40	22
SAREF4AGRI		55	49	13
SAREF4SYST		4	9	0

⁴¹ <https://github.com/smart-data-models/CrossSector>

⁴² <https://saref.etsi.org/>

SAREF Core

Figure 15. Overview of SAREF (Source: SmartM2M, ETSI TC, 2020)

The Smart Applications REFERENCE ontology (SAREF) is intended to enable interoperability between solutions from different providers and among various activity sectors in the Internet of Things (IoT). It specifies recurring core concepts in the Smart Applications domains, the main relationships between these concepts as well as axioms that constrain usage of these concepts and relationships. SAREF is built on the fundamental principles of *reuse and alignment* of concepts and relationships that are defined in existing assets; *modularity* to allow separation and recombination of different parts of the ontology depending on specific needs; *extensibility* to allow further growth of the ontology; and *maintainability* to facilitate the process of identifying and correcting defects, accommodate new requirements, and cope with changes in (parts of) SAREF (SmartM2M, ETSI TC, 2020). An illustrative overview of key concepts in SAREF Core is presented in Figure 15.

SAREF specifies the fundamental and generic concepts for “smart devices” such as sensors, meters, and appliances, and their reported measurements.

SAREF4WATR

SAREF4WATR extends the SAREF ontology for the water domain and aims to create a common core of general concepts for water data oriented to the IoT field (ETSI TC SmartM2M, 2020). As indicated by the blue classes in Figure 16, SAREF4WATR extends SAREF by adding water-related concepts, such as *WaterInfrastructure* being a subclass of *FeatureOfInterest* and *WaterDevice* added as a subclass of SAREF’s *Device*, while it inherits the fundamental concepts and the underlying semantics expressed in SAREF.

Figure 16. Overview of SAREF4WATR with some of the core classes of the ontology, relationships between them, and relations to other ontologies (yellow, pink and white). (Source: ETSI TC SmartM2M, 2020)

SAREF4AGRI

SAREF4AGRI is an extension of SAREF for the agriculture and food domain (SmartM2M, ETSI TS, 2020). It is built around two examples from the agricultural domain, namely livestock farming and smart irrigation.

Figure 17. Overview of SAREF4AGRI which shows some of the core classes of the ontology, relationships between them, and relations to other ontologies (yellow and white). (Source: SmartM2M, ETSI TS, 2020)

SAREF4SYST

SAREF4SYST (SmartM2M, ETSI TC, 2020) is a generic ontology module that defines an ontology pattern which can be instantiated for different domains. SAREF4SYST defines Systems, Connections between systems, and Connection Points at which systems may be connected. By the classes and properties of SAREF4SYST one may model how different systems relate (e.g., connecting sub-systems to main systems) and how different systems and their functions affect each other (e.g., the triggering of one function related to system A can affect a property of a system B).

Figure 18 Overview of SAREF4SYST (Source: SmartM2M, ETSI TC, 2020)

5.1.4 Other Ontologies

In addition to the SAREF ontologies described above, there are also other core ontologies and domain ontologies that might be relevant. These are described in the following items:

GeoSPARQL

GeoSPARQL⁴³ defines a vocabulary and a query language (extending SPARQL) for representing and retrieving geospatial data. It is a standard maintained by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC).

W3CTime

The W3C Time (OWL-Time) ontology⁴⁴ is an ontology for describing the temporal properties of resources in the world or described in Web pages. The ontology provides a vocabulary for expressing facts about topological (ordering) relations among instants and intervals, together with information about durations, and about temporal position including date-time information.

⁴³ <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql>

⁴⁴ <http://www.w3.org/2006/time#>

QUDT

The Quantities, Units, Dimensions and Types (QUDT) ontology defines classes, properties and restrictions for modelling physical quantities, units of measure and dimensions in different measurement systems, and implementing international standards for doing so⁴⁵. Figure 19. Illustration of the core design pattern of the QUDT ontology shows the overall design pattern used in the QUDT ontology.

Figure 19. Illustration of the core design pattern of the QUDT ontology⁴⁶

Relationship between Smart Data Models and ontologies

In a “basic” setting the direct link between the FIWARE data models and the ontologies is that concepts in the ontologies (or vocabularies) can be used to unambiguously define a context definition for data stored in a context broker according the FIWARE data model schemas. If, for example, there is an attribute *parcel*, which can have a different underlying meaning depending on the application domain, you can include as context in the payload that the value of *parcel* should be interpreted as *parcel* as defined by SAREF4AGRI ontology, as opposed to *parcel* defined by a freight logistics ontology, for example.

In a more “advanced” setting, where entities are represented in a context broker using some semantic data store, the ontologies have a much more prominent role. Using the NGSI-LD variant of the FIWARE data models, you can represent entities as triples (subject-relation-object) where subjects, relations, and objects are typed according to the ontology(ies), and this enables for example the ability to perform semantic search/data retrieval, generate knowledge graphs for further data analytics tasks, etc.

The smartdatamodels.org GitHub recently created a list of relevant sources for context, including the SAREF ontologies⁴⁷

⁴⁵ <http://www.qudt.org/pages/QUDToverviewPage.html>

⁴⁶ <http://www.qudt.org>

5.2 FIWARE contextual information solutions, NGSI

FIWARE plays an important role as an interoperability architecture in B-WaterSmart as well as other research projects in the water management domain. FIWARE offers an industry-independent interoperability architecture and a set of open-source generic enablers (software components) to implement technology platforms typically related to internet of things (IoT), so-called smart domains. One of the underlying standards is NGSI, an ETSI standardised protocol for managing contextual information to describe different entities of concern. NGSI is thus used to describe context information related to the entities stored in a FIWARE context broker.

There are basically two NGSI versions that are relevant, NGSIv2 and NGSI-LD. The main elements in the NGSIv2 model are entities, attributes and metadata, as shown in Figure 20. An entity represents a physical or logical object (e.g., a sensor, a person, an issue in a ticketing system) defined by an identifier and a type definition, an attribute represents some property of the entity (e.g., a measurement value), while the metadata describes additional “data about the data”, such as the accuracy of the measurement value.

Figure 20 NGSIv2 Conceptual Model ⁴⁸

The other version of NGSI, NGSI-LD, where LD stands for Linked Data, has a different underlying data model than NGSIv2. Here, data are described in triples in a subject-predicate-object pattern resulting in a graph representation of the context data. Furthermore, in NGSI-LD the ID of an entity should be a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) ensuring a consistent representation of the identifier of an entity.

Figure 21 shows the underlying model of NGSI-LD. As the figure shows, there is no metadata element, and the Attributes element in NGSIv2 now refers to either Property or Relationship where the former represents literal values (strings, decimals, etc.) while the latter represent relationships between different entities.

⁴⁷ https://github.com/smart-data-models/data-models/tree/master/context/ontologies_files

⁴⁸ <https://fiware.github.io/specifications/ngsiv2/stable/>

Figure 21 NGS-LD Conceptual Model ⁴⁹

NGSI-LD is the newest version of the protocol and defines an information model (including a meta model and a cross-domain ontology) derived from property graphs⁵⁰. This is further described in this ETSI white paper (Privat Gilles, 2021) along with a set of recommendations when modelling and using NGSI-LD. When using NGSI-LD as the underlying graph model in an NGSI-LD-compliant context broker, there are certain conventions or recommendations that should be followed. Two recommendations that are especially relevant are:

NGSI-LD users need to attach types to all the entities, relationships, and properties that they intend to instantiate in their implementations.

These types should be directly or indirectly derived from classes defined in shared OWL ontologies, thesauri, or taxonomies.

The reason why these two recommendations, and the use of domain ontologies, is so important is that ontologies serve to define a standardised and formalised description of entities in a way that enables both human and machine interpretation of data associated with real-life entities. This further

⁴⁹ https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/CIM/001_099/009/01.01.01_60/gs_CIM009v010101p.pdf

⁵⁰ The property graph model is used by popular graph databases such as Neo4J (<https://neo4j.com/>) and specifies a model made up of nodes, relationships, and properties (specifying data about the nodes and relationships).

allows entities to be integrated with other entities in and across domains, support data retrieval tasks, and allow inference of new knowledge from the data. In other words, applying the ontologies described in this report in combination with the NGSi-LD information model will facilitate data interpretation, data integration and relevant data retrieval and knowledge creation in the water management domain.

5.3 B-WaterSmart proposed data solutions per tool

As part of the Task 3.1 the input and output data of 22 tools developed in the framework of BWS project were collected in order to define the kind of input and output data that those tools use. An attempt to associate this data to smart data models provided by the [Smart Data Model Initiative](#) and detect which output data could be useful as input data to others has been made. This approach was undertaken to support interoperability by exposing data through data models, being compliant with the NGSi standard.

The collected information is available under following link: [Tool data information List](#)

One of the smart data models, which seems to be particularly useful for input data of BWS tools is [Water Distribution Management EPANET](#) model, which describes entities related to Water Network Management data, mainly obtained from the EPANET platform (tools: #17, #18, #24, #29, #30, #33.2). EPANET is a software application for modelling drinking water distribution systems developed by United States Environment Protection Agency (EPA). Another potentially useful data model for BWS interoperability is [WaterQualityObserved](#) (tools: #16, #19, #24, #25, #26, #29, #30), as it describes quality parameters at a certain water mass (river, lake, sea, etc.). The [Water observed](#) data model describes the following parameters: flow, volume and level of water observed, swell information and information on masses of floating objects and has been defined as potentially useful for input data of several BWS tools (#17, #24, #25, #22, #33.2, #35N). [Open channel management](#) describes entities related to structure of an Raw-Water (Open Channels) System Management domain and was defined as relevant to BWS tools #29, #30 and #21. [Device](#) model consists of a set of entities that allow the representation of devices, like camera, sensor, mobile, etc and might be of use for tools #29 and 30. The [Waste water](#) model contains entities related to the process of waste water treatment and therefore might be of use in relation to interoperability of tools #16 , #30. It is worth pointing out that for several tools more than one data model seems applicable for the input data.

It has been observed that several tools output data could match with the Water Consumption Model, namely tools # 24, #20, #22, #28 and #33.2. Water Consumption Model has 1 entity type: WaterConsumptionObserved that captures following information related to the performance of smart water meters: different customer side leak alarms, flow rate and water consumption.

5.4 B-WaterSmart new smart data model: Water smartness

An analysis of Smart Data Models from the water domain discussed in Section 5.1.2 was performed in the context of a possible basis for the creation of a smart data model describing water smartness. The first effort to define a smart model for water smartness was made as presented in Figure 22 with full example of an entity in JSON-LD format that follows the NGSi-LD standard available in [ANNEX D](#). In this first attempt to build a smart data model describing water smartness, the

WaterQualityObserved data model was modified to incorporate the elements of the initial backbone structure of the water-smartness assessment framework: assessment criteria, strategic objectives and metrics, as presented in MS16 “First version of the assessment framework”, which is V0 - a prototype for testing by LLs in the scope of T1.4. Selected metrics from MS16 were used to prepare the presented example of an entity. More precisely, the strategic objective A. *Ensuring water supply for all relevant uses* and the related Assessment criteria: A.1 *Safe and secure fit for-purpose water supply*, A.2. *Accessibility and equity (for people and for other uses)*, A.3 *Financial viability* and assigned metrics together with respective units are included in the example entity. For the metrics unit code is used, wherever applicable. The values and coordinates used for the example are random.

```

2   "id": "urn:ngsi-ld:EnsuringWater:ensuringwater:Athens:A",
3   "type": "EnsuringWater",
4   "description": "Ensuring water for all relevant uses",
5   "location": {
6     "type": "GeoProperty",
7     "value": {
8       "type": "Point",
9       "coordinates": [
10      -5.993307,
11      37.362882
12    ]
13  }
14  },
15  "hasWaterProvision": {
16    "type": "Relationship",
17    "object": "urn:ngsi-ld:WaterQualityObserved:waterqualityobserved:Athens:A1"
18  },
19  "hasAccessibilityAndEquity": {
20    "type": "Relationship",
21    "object": "urn:ngsi-ld:WaterQualityObserved:waterqualityobserved:Athens:A2"
22  },
23  "hasFinancialViability": {
24    "type": "Relationship",
25    "object": "urn:ngsi-ld:WaterQualityObserved:waterqualityobserved:Athens:A3"
26  },
27  "@context": [
28    "https://smartdatamodels.org/context.jsonld",
29    "https://uri.etsi.org/ngsi-ld/v1/ngsi-ld-core-context.jsonld"
30  ]

```

Figure 22 The first lines of the example of an entity in JSON-LD format that follows NGSI-LD standard available in Annex D

The assessment of the possibility of building a smart data model describing water smartness based on the water-smartness assessment framework is on-going in the context of possible use for Task 3.9 (Develop and deploy the water-smartness dashboard). The development of the water-smartness assessment framework is an iterative process, on-going at the time of preparation of D3.1. Once the final list of metrics is available, as a result of work within tasks 6.3 and 6.2, development of a water smartness data model based on an updated water-smartness assessment framework will be considered. Depending on the needs, the development of a new smart data model or building on existing ones might be examined as well.

6 B-WaterSmart implementation results

6.1 Initial overview of BWS Tools

6.1.1 Initial survey for technical baseline definition

One of the first steps done in was to create a survey in collaboration with other WPs, especially the one related to exploitation and communication and dissemination, to collect data about the tools. The Survey was created online to facilitate the access to any project partner at any time and Microsoft forms hosted by Eurecat was used as technical solution to format the survey. It was delivered on December 2020 and it ended with information about 15 tools from the final number of 22 tools involved in the project. In the scope of this task the aim was to start collecting technical details about the tools and ambitions on interoperability that could be managed during the project. The questions of the survey are presented in **ANNEX C: Questions of initial survey**. The table of the main results is presented in the file [Survey on B-WaterSmart Tools](#). The file is stored on the Nextcloud platform as document sharing solution for the BWS project.

As relevant information we were able to retrieve the number of tools located in each LL. At the beginning of the task the number of tools were 15. However, during the development of the task more tools were added to a total amount of 22 as shown previously in this deliverable.

Figure 23 Number of tools per LL

As shown in Figure 23 the LL supporting the highest number of tools is located in Lisbon, due to the number of tools provided by the partner “Baseform”, responsible for 4 tools in total. The tag cloud in Figure 24 shows the project partners responsible for the tools. The size of their names is related with the number of tools they have applied.

Figure 24 Tag cloud of project partners responsible for tools

Based on the general description of the tools provided by each tool owner, the Microsoft forms tool provides us with a tag cloud, being the more repeated word the boldest and highest one. So, it can be easily concluded that most of the tools (in fact 12/15) were using the tag “water” to describe themselves, which is quite normal in the scope of B-WaterSmart project. However, the other highlighted tags (water efficiency, water scarcity, water demand, water cycle, water consumption, water network, water resources and risk assessment) were useful too, to assess which possible data models may be needed.

Figure 25 Overview of keywords of applied tools

At that point, it was crucial to better understand the characteristics of the tools, to later develop specifications and guidelines to achieve interoperability. Therefore, at first, we collected information related with the execution model of the tools as shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26 Execution mode results

As we can see we obtained 2 answers in “Others” group, which one answer was “not yet defined” and the second was “Web application” specifying that “FIWARE has not been evaluated for their case”. So, to be consistent, the second “other” answer should be considered as a client-server application.

Regarding the interoperability approach adopted by each tool and considering the mechanisms used for information exchange, and the format of input / output data, we obtained the information shown in Figure 27.

Figure 27 Mechanisms for information exchange

For a proper development of the task, one of the most important aspects was to define the technical baseline regarding interoperability features of each tool. Such information was required to understand which kind of data converters, may be needed depending on the target interoperability maturity level of each tool. The initial situation is shown in Figure 28 and Figure 29.

Figure 28 Input data format

Figure 29 Output data format

Considering “Other” as the majority answer, the responses included in this group were completed with comments like: “Not defined yet” and “All”. It is necessary to say that this survey was sent at the very beginning of the project where most of the tools were under conceptual definition. So, it is understandable this kind of requirements were not yet defined.

In order to define the potential work to do during the project, a question regarding “interoperability ambition” during the project was added. As we can see depicted in Figure 30 the majority answer was “Full interoperability” followed by “Medium interoperability” and “No interoperability”. Thus, at the beginning of the project there were 8 tools expecting to be interoperable at some level.

Figure 30 Initial interoperability ambition

6.1.2 Initial implementation approach

Considering the initial situation described in the previous point, the main work consisted of assessing the available options to achieve interoperability in the tools and between the tools and examining the maturity level of each one. For this aim, the initial plan was to split the tools into two working groups based on the information provided on the following topics: the compatibility with FIWARE, the interoperability ambition and the technical stage (how mature the tool was) of the tool. These three parameters are the three main evaluations columns presented in Table 6

Then, it was developed a color code to reflect the importance of these items and to highlight the need efforts to achieve a high interoperability maturity level. The explanation of each color code is given in the following lines:

- **Green (✓):** Low work effort
- **Orange (✓/✗):** Tentatively low effort or missing information
- **Red (✗):** High work effort and missing information

After that, based on the color code explained before we determined the priority to approach the tool owners creating two different groups as represented in Table 6:

- **1st Group:** at least 2 items in green or 3 items in orange. In theory the most advanced and with higher interoperability ambition
- **2nd Group:** 1 item in orange.

Table 6 First overview and working groups strategy

Tool	FIWARE compatibility	Ambition	Technical current solution	Proposed priority	Group
(#16) The Water Reuse & Sludge Management Digital Solution Platform	✓		✓/✗	✓/✗	2 nd WG
(#17) Environment for decision support and selection of alternative actions	✓	✓	✓/✗	✓	1 st WG
(#18) RE-ACTOR	✓/✗	✓/✗	✓/✗	✓	
(#20) UWC Observatory	✗	✗		✗	
(#22) UWOT	✗			✗	

(#23) Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS tool					
(#24) Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model	✓		✓/x	✓/x	2 nd WG
(#25) Water-energy-P balance planning	✓		✓/x	✓/x	
(#26) QMRA+	x	x			
(#27) RA-Reuse	✓		✓/x	✓/x	2 nd WG
(#28) Short-Term Demand Forecasting Tool					
(#29) iWidget+ Platform	✓/x	✓	✓	✓	1 st WG
(#32) Digital Enabler	✓	✓	✓	✓	
(#33) Climate-readiness Certification tool	✓	✓	✓/x	✓	
(#30) Azure Cosmos DB and Environmental Dashboard	x	✓/x		x	2 nd WG

So with this two groups of tools, we initiated a set of 2 rounds of meetings, one for each WG. Then, since there was no contractual obligation for tool owners to upgrade their tools to be interoperable, one of the tasks was to promote interoperability and the use of FIWARE. Since many tools were still in the development stage, this was the right time for them to adapt FIWARE components and embrace their advantages.

In the meantime, during the project, the initial plans in terms of interoperability, ambition, and use of FIWARE have changed by some tools. The extended and needed time to agree on tool conceptualization, and features to implement, limited the amount of resources that could be dedicated for interoperability developments. However, regarding the use of FIWARE, some tools that do not use FIWARE yet, are committed to adapt their tools at any time in the future.

6.2 B-WaterSmart tool interoperability examples

In this section three examples from three different living labs are presented. All of them are potential examples of interoperability at different maturity levels that are intended to be implemented during the B-WaterSmart project duration. Other example may arise during the project scope and could be reported on later deliverables.

6.2.1 East Frisia Living Lab

The three different tools developed and used within Living Lab East Frisia are focusing different time horizons, scales and parts of the water demand and resources forecasting process. Hence, they are very much complementary to each other, serving, in total, the overall aim of providing a comprehensive picture of water demands' and water resources' situation within the scope of the living lab.

The short-term demand forecasting tool (#28) is designed to estimate the short-term demand of domestic and small industrial users in a specific region. As there is not all information to prepare a short-term demand forecast bottom-up, the short-term demand forecasting tool will make mainly use of smart meter data in order to derive the required information for a long-term water demand forecast. The short-term demand forecasting tool (#28) and UWOT (#22) are therefore complementary in the way, the latest UWOT stand-alone, working version of the model will be used to provide a long-term forecast of the household's water demand considering different scenarios of future water usage based on the information derived from the short-term demand forecasting tool (#28). Finally, the demand information from UWOT will be used together with tabular data from open source data on water resources and other stakeholder's demands, along with stakeholder inputs on socio-economic and technical parameters as input data for the Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS Tool (#23). In the end, the Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS Tool (#23) can be used to explore alternative water demand and supply options under different climatic as well as demand and resources change scenarios. The communication across the different tools will be facilitate via CSV files.

Despite the three tools used in the East Frisian Living Lab are not using all FIWARE based solutions to allow its interoperability, the living lab's systemic solution as a whole is a good example of interaction between tools that are enhancing their capabilities, and indeed is an example of interoperability maturity level 1.

6.2.2 Lisbon Living Lab

The Lisbon Living Lab is the one with the highest number of tools involved, so it could be the place where the interoperability among their tools could have more impact on decision making processes in the region. To complete section once feedback from Lisbon LL is given.

In this Living lab there is a major technological provider, Baseform. It has 4 different tools involved and it is expected the interaction between them as highlighted in Figure 31. Interoperability ambition among Baseform tools on Lisbon Living Lab.

Granularity: city/ city zone/ city facility

Figure 31. Interoperability ambition among Baseform tools on Lisbon Living Lab

However, there has been also technical conversations to allow the interoperability among Tool #17 and the Tool #20, developed by Lisboa E-Nova, to integrate in the Decisional environments data from both systems and also the exchange of data from Tool #20 to Tool #25 and possibly the opposite as well.

6.2.3 Venice Living Lab

The interoperability approach adopted in the Venice LL is inherited by the Digital Enabler, and in particular by its FIWARE-based components. The Digital Enabler can be seen as a set of coherent components that allow the management of data along its life-cycle, from collection, to preparation, analysis, sharing and visualization. In particular, the platforms developed in the Venice LL will leverage some components for data preparation and harmonization, aiming at, whenever possible, making data compatible with NGSI-LD, exposing some of them on a Context Broker and allowing third party systems to subscribe to its entities.

The Figure 21 f provides a preliminary view of the architectural components that will enable such an approach. Data is collected from heterogeneous data sources and pre-processed to guarantee data quality and harmonization. The data is stored in ad-hoc data repositories, specialized for each type of data (raster images, JSON, csv, time-series, etc.). When possible, data is transformed according to NGSI-LD standard and to available Smart Data Models to be managed by the FIWARE Orion Context Broker, a core component of the Digital Enabler. Data is then used for feeding functionalities of tools #16 and #19 and specifically for their components dedicated to data analytic and data visualization.

Figure 32. Schema of Venice interoperability approach

7 Conclusions and recommendations

The deliverable 3.1 offers a complete guide to any tool willing to implement an interoperable roadmap following its contents. It covers aspects such as: a) basic definitions and concepts, b) the study of the current status of real tools c) the study of reference software architectures and d) the study of available domain data models for water related tools. All these steps are needed to implement the steps defined in the interoperability guidelines to achieve certain interoperability maturity level.

The document shows real examples based on the 22 tools involved in the 5 Living labs LL of the project: Venice, Bodø, Flanders, Alicante, East Frisia and Lisbon project. Each tool has been assessed, with the respective tool owner providing a descriptive factsheet together with the main use cases and a final assessment of requirements and interoperability maturity levels. In addition, for each tool, a set of smart data models compatible with FIWARE is proposed to be used and the current and future implementation status during the project on some Living labs is presented.

The adoption of interoperability roadmaps could be quite challenging starting from legacy tools or even from scratch if the teams have no experience or don't receive any support. However, the reference architecture proposes solutions to tackle these situations and allow its implementation. In terms of data models, the number of accessible data models is growing and evolving every day, making them more reliable and widely used. The implementation of interoperability solutions has not been mandatory in the project, and therefore not all tools will be FIWARE compatible at the end of the project but most of them will make a step forward in the B-WaterSmart maturity levels scale.

The document also introduced the concept of B-WaterSmart/Interoperability maturity levels that aims to provide a reference classification for any tool considering their interoperable capabilities and provides a common roadmap to follow in the interoperability ambition of any development team based on the usage of FIWARE technologies

Finally, the document introduces an example of a new data model. The possibility of building a smart data model describing water smartness for visualization of the Water-smartness assessment framework by T3.9 will be further assessed once the task begins. The new model in accordance with Tool#34 and the work done in WP6 could be either build on existing one(s), but development of a new smart data model will be considered as well. All that will be performed according to the needs and decided at later stage. Additionally, the work performed and described in the D3.1 related to the categorization of B-WaterSmart tools based on the FIWARE maturity levels is valuable for the dashboard development, as the dashboard itself will be powered by FIWARE and the compatibility of relevant solutions could further enhance the benefits provided by the tool.

8 References

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9 ANNEX A: B-WaterSmart Tool Factsheets

The content of this annex is not included to avoid a larger size of this document and a link of the content is provided: [**B-WaterSmart Tool data Information List**](#)

The file is stored in Nextcloud platform as document sharing solution for BWS project.

Most of the tools portrayed on fact sheets were on development at the time to complete the information and some features, so the reader could find some descriptions not reported. Some fact sheets are uncompleted; however, they contain enough information to have a clear idea of what the tools are meant to and its capabilities.

10 ANNEX B: Tools use cases

The content of this annex is not included to avoid a larger size of this document and a link of the content is provided: **[Use Cases Functionalities of all tools](#)**

The file is stored in Nextcloud platform as document sharing solution for BWS project.

11 ANNEX C: Questions of initial survey

The following questions were defined to assess the initial overview of the tools, basic and technical information and the willingness of interoperability and the use of FIWARE. The questionnaire was created also in collaboration with other partners for exploitation and dissemination purposes.

Some of the questions, were not answered at the beginning of the project because the tool owners didn't have the proper information as the initial designs and contacts were happening, and due to a lack of knowledge about some topics like interoperability, requirements or FIWARE.

The questions that were sent were the following:

- Tool name
- Partner responsible of the tool
- The Tool name is the same used in the Proposal? If not, please specify the name in the proposal.
- Living Lab/Case Study using it
- Data application product Number.
- General description
- Version
- Use in the living Lab/use-case
- Relations of the Tool to domains and technologies in the Circular Economy
- Tags and keywords related with the Tool
- Technical contact
- Is the tool composed by different modules that should be differentiated?
- In case you want to differentiate different modules of your tool, please provide a detailed explanation of each module: purpose, technology used, users, current interoperability level
- Is your Tool FIWARE Compatible
- Which FIWARE compatible technical solution have you implemented?
- Is the tool based on a server (on cloud or on premise) or it is a standalone application?
- Which type of user interface you have
- Which are the technical requirements to run your tool? (Operating System, browser, ...)
- Is authentication/registration needed?
- Which kind of mechanism are used for information exchange in your Tool?
- Which type of INPUT data format is used?
- Which type INPUT data (external data sources, models, services) are you planning to integrate, or you could you need to integrate to improve your tool?
- Could you share a link to an INPUT file?
- Which type of OUTPUT data format is used?
- Which type of OUTPUT data (data sources, models, services, ...) could you provide to other tools?
- Could you share a link to an OUTPUT file?
- Could you identify the interoperability standards used in your tool?
- Do you want to explain how do you use them?
- Interoperability ambition of the tool to achieve during the B-WaterSmart project

- Are you using JSON-LD?
- Can you give us more information about your JSON-LD work?
- Are you willing to collaborate on defining a JSON-LD specification for this tool?
- Could you define the information workflow of the tool?
- IPR holder
- Dissemination level
- Expected impacts
- IPR option
- Non-Commercial exploitation route
- Commercial exploitation route
- Added value expected with exploitation route:
- TRL at the beginning of the project:
- Expected TRL at the end of the project:
- Prototype is ready to be applied by:
- Support in exploitation is requested:
- When is support expected? And email contact
- Costs
- License type for FLOSS tools
- CC license type
- Dissemination responsible
- What does the tool do?
- What are the challenges addressed by it?
- What is the innovation?
- What is the target audience (intended users) for the tool?
- Please add link to further information about the tool:
- What is the official related B-WaterSmart deliverable number?
- Please upload image related to tool and useful for dissemination here
- Relevant publications

12 ANNEX D: B-WaterSmart new smart data model for water smartness - example of an entity of JSON-LD format that follows NGS-LD standard (based on Strategic objective A. Ensuring water for all relevant uses as presented in MS16)

```

{
  "id": "urn:ngsi-ld:EnsuringWater:ensuringwater:Athens:A",
  "type": "EnsuringWater",
  "description": "Ensuring water for all relevant uses",
  "location": {
    "type": "GeoProperty",
    "value": {
      "type": "Point",
      "coordinates": [
        -5.993307,
        37.362882
      ]
    }
  },
  "hasWaterProvision": {
    "type": "Relationship",
    "object": "urn:ngsi-ld:WaterQualityObserved:waterqualityobserved:Athens:A1"
  },
  "hasAccessibilityAndEquity": {
    "type": "Relationship",
    "object": "urn:ngsi-ld:WaterQualityObserved:waterqualityobserved:Athens:A2"
  },
  "hasFinancialViability": {
    "type": "Relationship",
    "object": "urn:ngsi-ld:WaterQualityObserved:waterqualityobserved:Athens:A3"
  },
  "@context": [
    "https://smartdatamodels.org/context.jsonld",
    "https://uri.etsi.org/ngsi-ld/v1/ngsi-ld-core-context.jsonld"
  ]
}

{
  "id": "urn:ngsi-ld:WaterQualityObserved:waterqualityobserved:Athens:A1",
  "type": "WaterQualityObserved",
  "description": "Safe and secure fit-for-purpose water provision",
  "dateObserved": {
    "type": "Property",
    "value": {
      "@type": "DateTime",

```

```

        "@value": "2017-01-31T06:45:00Z"
      }
    },
    "location": {
      "type": "GeoProperty",
      "value": {
        "type": "Point",
        "coordinates": [
          -5.993307,
          37.362882
        ]
      }
    },
    "measurand": {
      "type": "Property",
      "value": [
        "water resource exploitation, alternative water resource
exploitation, safe drinking water, compliant reclaimed water, security and
resilience"
      ]
    },
    "waterResource": {
      "type": "Property",
      "value": 24.4,
      "metadata": {
        "unitCode": {
          "value": "P1"
        }
      }
    },
    "alternativeWaterResource": {
      "type": "Property",
      "value": 78,
      "metadata": {
        "unitCode": {
          "value": "P1"
        }
      }
    },
    "safeDrinkingWater": {
      "type": "Property",
      "value": 49,
      "metadata": {
        "unitCode": {

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        "value": "P1"
      }
    }
  },
  "reclaimedWater": {
    "type": "Property",
    "value": 80,
    "metadata": {
      "unitCode": {
        "value": "P1"
      }
    }
  },
  "securityResilience": {
    "type": "Property",
    "value": 80,
    "metadata": {
      "unitCode": {
        "value": P1
      }
    }
  },
  "hasEnsuringWater": {
    "type": "Relationship",
    "object": "urn:ngsi-ld:EnsuringWater:ensuringwater:Athens:A"
  },
  "@context": [
    "https://smartrdatamodels.org/context.jsonld",
    "https://uri.etsi.org/ngsi-ld/v1/ngsi-ld-core-context.jsonld"
  ]
}

{
  "id": "urn:ngsi-ld:WaterQualityObserved:waterqualityobserved:Athens:A2",
  "type": "WaterQualityObserved",
  "description": "Accessibility and equity (for people and for other
uses)",
  "dateObserved": {
    "type": "Property",
    "value": {
      "@type": "DateTime",
      "@value": "2017-01-31T06:45:00Z"
    }
  }
}

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    }
  },
  "location": {
    "type": "GeoProperty",
    "value": {
      "type": "Point",
      "coordinates": [
        -5.993307,
        37.362882
      ]
    }
  },
  "measurand": {
    "type": "Property",
    "value": [
      "physical access to households and small businesses, physical
      access to public spaces, physical access industrial, agriculture access,
      number of points with potential conflict"
    ]
  },
  "accessHousehold": {
    "type": "Property",
    "value": 24.4
    "metadata": {
      "unitCode": {
        "value": "MTQ"
      }
    }
  },
  "accessPublic": {
    "type": "Property",
    "value": 3
    "metadata": {
      "unitCode": {
        "value": "#/km2"
      }
    }
  },
  "accessIndustrial": {
    "type": "Property",
    "value": 67.4,
    "metadata": {
      "unitCode": {
        "value": "P1"
      }
    }
  }
}

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        }
      },
      "accessAgriculture": {
        "type": "Property",
        "value": 67.4,
        "metadata": {
          "unitCode": {
            "value": "P1"
          }
        }
      },
      "conflictPoints": {
        "type": "Property",
        "value": 9,
      },
      "hasEnsuringWater": {
        "type": "Relationship",
        "object": "urn:ngsi-ld:EnsuringWater:ensuringwater:Athens:A"
      },
      "@context": [
        "https://smartdatamodels.org/context.jsonld",
        "https://uri.etsi.org/ngsi-ld/v1/ngsi-ld-core-context.jsonld"
      ]
    }
  }
  {
    "id": "urn:ngsi-ld:WaterQualityObserved:waterqualityobserved:Athens:A3",
    "type": "WaterQualityObserved",
    "description": "Financial viability",
    "dateObserved": {
      "type": "Property",
      "value": {
        "@type": "DateTime",
        "@value": "2017-01-31T06:45:00Z"
      }
    },
    "location": {
      "type": "GeoProperty",
      "value": {
        "type": "Point",
        "coordinates": [

```

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        -5.993307,  
        37.362882  
    ]  
  },  
  "measurand": {  
    "type": "Property",  
    "value": [  
      "willingness to pay, affordability, financial continuation"  
    ]  
  },  
  "willingnessToPay": {  
    "type": "Property",  
    "value": 4,  
  },  
  "affordability": {  
    "type": "Property",  
    "value": 3  
  },  
  "financialContinuation": {  
    "type": "Property",  
    "value": 3  
  },  
  "hasEnsuringWater": {  
    "type": "Relationship",  
    "object": "urn:ngsi-ld:EnsuringWater:ensuringwater:Athens:A"  
  },  
  "@context": [  
    "https://smartdatamodels.org/context.jsonld",  
    "https://uri.etsi.org/ngsi-ld/v1/ngsi-ld-core-context.jsonld"  
  ]  
}
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869171. The publication reflects only the authors' views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.